

Topic: CIRC BIO-01-01 Circular Cities and Regions Initiative's project development assistance (CCRI-PDA)

D1.2 – Guide to good practices and opportunities at the European and National level

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D1.2 – Guide to good practices and opportunities at the European and National level

Deliverable	DX.Y – Title of the deliverable
Work package No. and Title	WP1 Systemic engagement of local communities' and political commitment
Task No. and Title	T1.2 – Practices and opportunities at national and European levels
Start Date:	02.02.2023
Revision Date:	28.08.2023 11.07.2024
Release Date:	30.08.2023 V1 19.07.2024 V2
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Status (F: final; D: draft; RD: revised draft)	F
Dissemination level	PU – Public
Document ID / File Name	DECISO_D1.2_for final review
Abstract	This deliverable describes the Good Practices identified at different scales (from the national to the European level) applicable to the pilot areas for the development of the pilots' circular economy programs. It relates to Task "T1.2 – Practices and opportunities at national and European levels".
Title and number of connected deliverables	D1.3 – Reports from mobilization and mutual learning workshops in the pilot areas
Explain Deliverable Dependency/ Connection	This deliverable is a guide that includes Good Practices related to the topic of the pilot areas at national and European level and their Opportunities, that can provide tools for the development of the four pilot's circular economy programs.
Title of connected external documents	N/A
Reference of the document and the link (if available)	N/A

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1. Objective and Purpose

The objective of the DECISO project is to foster the interest of potential investors and to create a favourable climate for the development of the Circular Economy (CE).

DECISO – DEvelopers of Circular Solutions” is funded by the European Commission under the Horizon Europe program, Topic: CIRCBIO-01-01 Circular Cities and Regions Initiative’s project development assistance, Grant Agreement N° 101082232)

Purpose of DECISO project is to accompany and assist promoters with actions for mobilising stakeholders to promote systemic solutions that involve all actors of the value chain of an asset, and also, all those who can influence, even indirectly, the value and the emergence of Ecosystems of CE.

The objective of the current Deliverable 1.2 is the development of a Guide that describes Good Practices (GPs) related to the circular economy programs of the pilot areas together with their opportunities, as identified and classified by the project partners at the National and European levels.

The purpose is to provide the DECISO project partners (and any other interested in the specific circular economy topic party) with an accumulative Guide, where various Good Practices (at the partners’ national level, as also at the EU level) can be found and can provide information on successful projects and case studies. Opportunities of GPs to give inputs and feedback or be even (partly) transferred as opportunities at the European and the National levels, are also presented. Through the identification of applicable practices and their opportunities (coming out from each GP Transfer Potential – Replicability section) at national and European level, the Guide can provide inspiration, ideas, and tools for the development of the four pilots’ circular economy programs.

The steps followed for the development of this Deliverable are depicted in Figure 1 and are described in detail in Section 2.

Figure 1: Steps followed for the development of Deliverable 1.2

2. Description of steps followed for the elaboration of the Guide

Step 1. All partners worked through desk research and selected main information for any possible Good Practice (GP) related to their pilot area policy topic. They all followed a template ([Annex I](#)) prepared by the Task Leader and approved by the partnership. All partners were asked to fill in the information in detail

about a minimum of three (3) GPs per pilot area. The Task Leader collected all partners’ contributions provided by the end of April 2023 and saved them in the projects’ repository (TEAMS environment).

Step 2. A participatory workshop was organized at the European level (M7) by ACR+ in Brussels, involving European experts of the European Commission (EC), of European Research Executive Agency (REA) and sister projects such as HOOP project, to identify and discuss Good Practices and their opportunities. All partners that attended the workshop tried to identify new GPs to be influenced from or collected more information on those already gathered during Step 1.

Step 3. Following the Step 2 activities, more GPs were added by some partners. Improvements were also made in those GPs that were identified during the 1st step. For this purpose, the DECISO partners exchanged knowledge with sister projects’ representatives, as also with other related European and national level initiatives, which were identified during the Brussels workshop. The exchanges made, included brief interviews and storytelling initiatives, following for this purpose a new template provided by the Task Leader ([Annex II](#)).

Step 4. A final national participatory workshop was organized (by M9 for all partners) in each pilot area to identify and discuss more possible new Good Practices and their opportunities at the national level, following the same template used during Step 3. The participants of the workshops had also the chance to be informed on all previous good practices identified in each pilot area. All partners finalized their inputs after these national level workshops in the project Good Practise repository, having the endorsement of their regional level stakeholders.

Step 5. The Good Practices and their opportunities that were collected in the former steps, were elaborated by the Task Leader in order to produce the current Guide.

3. Good Practices Cummulative Table and Classification

Following the aforementioned procedure, 17 GPs were collected in total. Table 1 is a cumulative table including the titles of the Good Practices (at National and European level) per partner and per DECISO pilot area.

Table 1: Good Practices Titles per Pilot partner

No	Author / partner	Title of the GP
GP1	Stephanie Keßler - Sabine Herrmann / FREIE UND HANSESTADT HAMBURG	PROFI Environment (PROFI Umwelt) (single beneficiary) PROFI Environment Transfer (PROFI Umwelt Transfer) (cooperation projects)
GP2	Stephanie Keßler / FREIE UND HANSESTADT HAMBURG	Circular Cities (past programme) ClimAccelerator (EIT Climate-KIC)
GP3	Sabine Herrmann / FREIE UND HANSESTADT HAMBURG	BNW circular hubs
GP4	Sabine Herrmann / FREIE UND HANSESTADT HAMBURG	IFB Innovations starter (IFB Innovationsstarter)
GP5	Sabine Herrmann / FREIE UND HANSESTADT HAMBURG	circularinvest
GP6	Sofia Martins / IRRADIARE	URSA Project - Alqueva By-Products Recirculation Units

GP7	Sofia Martins / IRRADIARE	AgroPaper, a sustainable and biodegradable solution for the agricultural mulching technique
GP8	Sofia Martins / IRRADIARE	Fossil-Energy-Free Technologies and Strategies (FEFTS)
GP9	Julia Oberdörffer / OLDENBURGISCH-OSTFRIESISCHER WASSERVERBAND	Rainwater Treatment Systems
GP10	Daniel Gerdes / OLDENBURGISCH-OSTFRIESISCHER WASSERVERBAND	SAWA's Climate Resilience Framework
GP11	Yannick Tiemann / OLDENBURGISCH-OSTFRIESISCHER WASSERVERBAND	Rooftop Garden and Greenhouse Urban Farming
GP12	Julia Oberdörffer / OLDENBURGISCH-OSTFRIESISCHER WASSERVERBAND	Evolving Regions Collaborative Roadmapping
GP13	Konstantinos Kiriakopoulos / Municipal District Heating Company of the Wider Region of Amynteo	Use of alternative raw materials and fuels in cement Industry (TITAN GROUP Industry)
GP14	Konstantinos Kiriakopoulos / Municipal District Heating Company of the Wider Region of Amynteo	Poznan Energy from Waste Plant, Poland
GP15	Konstantinos Kiriakopoulos / Municipal District Heating Company of the Wider Region of Amynteo	Econotre eco-centre
GP16	Athina Krestou / University of Western Macedonia (PDM)	Innovative Technologies for Ecological and Efficient Pyrolysis of Waste Treatment
GP17	Athina Krestou / University of Western Macedonia (PDM)	The Revised National Waste Management Plan for the period 2020-2030

A **classification** of all the identified Good Practices and their Opportunities followed, including the pilot topic, the geographical scope, the transfer potential / replicability of the GP as opportunity and, if applicable, the clear evidence of success. This classification is presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Classification of Good Practices

No	Pilot Topic	Good Practice	Geographical scope national/ regional/ international	Transfer Potential – Replicability as Opportunity for each partner: yes/no/not clear	Clear evidence of success: yes/no
GP1	STRATEGIC FRAMEWORK FOR FINANCIAL SCHEMES	PROFI Environment (PROFI Umwelt) (single beneficiary) PROFI Environment Transfer (PROFI Umwelt Transfer) (cooperation projects)	Regional	Yes	Yes

GP2	STRATEGIC FRAMEWORK FOR FINANCIAL SCHEMES	Circular Cities (past programme) ClimAccelerator (EIT Climate-KIC)	International	Not clear	Yes
GP3	STRATEGIC FRAMEWORK FOR FINANCIAL SCHEMES	BNW circular hubs	National	Yes	Yes
GP4	STRATEGIC FRAMEWORK FOR FINANCIAL SCHEMES	IFB Innovations starter (IFB Innovationsstarter)	Regional	Yes	Yes
GP5	STRATEGIC FRAMEWORK FOR FINANCIAL SCHEMES	circularinvest	International	Yes	Yes
GP6	CIRCULAR AGRI-FOOD BUSINESS MODELS	URSA Project - Alqueva By-Products Recirculation Units	Regional	Yes	Yes
GP7	CIRCULAR AGRI-FOOD BUSINESS MODELS	AgroPaper, a sustainable and biodegradable solution for the agricultural mulching technique	International	Yes	Not clear
GP8	CIRCULAR AGRI-FOOD BUSINESS MODELS	Fossil-Energy-Free Technologies and Strategies (FEFTS)	International	Yes	Yes
GP9	OPTIMISE RAINWATER USE	Plant Rainwater Treatment Systems	National	Not clear	Yes
GP10	OPTIMISE RAINWATER USE	SAWA's Climate Resilience Framework	International	Yes	Yes
GP11	OPTIMISE RAINWATER USE	Rooftop Garden and Greenhouse Urban Farming	International	Not clear	No
GP12	OPTIMISE RAINWATER USE	Evolving Regions Collaborative Roadmapping	International	Yes	Yes
GP13	DECARBONISATION AND POST-LIGNITE TRANSITION	Use of alternative raw materials and fuels in cement Industry (TITAN GROUP Industry)	National	Yes	Yes
GP14	DECARBONISATION AND POST-LIGNITE TRANSITION	Poznan Energy from Waste Plant, Poland	International	Yes	Yes

GP15	DECARBONISATION AND POST-LIGNITE TRANSITION	Econotre eco-centre	International	Yes	Yes
GP16	DECARBONISATION AND POST-LIGNITE TRANSITION	Innovative Technologies for Ecological and Efficient Pyrolysis of Waste Treatment	International	Yes	Not clear
GP17	DECARBONISATION AND POST-LIGNITE TRANSITION	The Revised National Waste Management Plan for the period 2020-2030	National	Yes	No

The following sections describe in detail the GPs per pilot area as collected. Opportunities per pilot area are also described.

4. Detailed description of Good Practices and Opportunities for Pilot 1. FREIE UND HANSESTADT HAMBURG

4.1. Detailed description of Good Practices

The Good Practices related to Pilot 1, are presented in detail in Tables 3-7.

Table 3. Detailed description of GP1. PROFI Umwelt

1. Author contact information		
Full Name	Stephanie Keßler / Sabine Herrmann	
E-mail	stephanie.kessler@sk.hamburg.de / sabine.herrmann1@sk.hamburg.de	
Telephone	-	
2. Organisation providing the Description		
Country	Germany	
Region	Hamburg	
Website	www.ifbhh.de	
3. Public or private body responsible of the Practice		
Name of the organisation being the main public or private body in charge of this practice	<i>IFB Hamburg – Investment and Funding Bank of Hamburg (public-law institution) & BUKEA (Authority for the Environment, Climate, Energy and Agriculture in Hamburg)</i>	
Location of the responsible public or private body:	Country	Germany
	Region/City	Hamburg
4. Good Practice general information		
Title of the Practice	PROFI Environment (PROFI Umwelt) (single beneficiary)PROFI Environment Transfer (PROFI Umwelt Transfer) (cooperation projects)	
Web link	https://www.ifbhh.de/programme/gruender-and-unternehmen/energie-und-ressourcen-einsparen-	

	gu/ressourcenschonende-produkte-entwickeln/profi-umwelt-und-profi-umwelt-transfer	
Timescale (start/end month/year)	Since 2014	
Name the project where this practice come is coming from	n/a	
Name the project acronym	n/a	
Thematic objective of the Practice	Development of innovative products, procedures or services that contribute to climate and environment protection. First and foremost, saving resources and material as well as improving circular economy.	
Geographical scope of the Practice	Local/ Regional / National / International, but with focus on enterprises based in Hamburg	
Location of the Practice	Country	Germany
	Region/City	Hamburg
5. Good Practice elements		
Abstract of the Practice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Funding for enterprises of any size, from every sector and in any thematic field/area of technology established in Hamburg as well as cooperating universities and research institutions. Up to EUR 500.00 (single beneficiaries) and EUR 1M (cooperation projects) for innovative projects contributing to resource efficiency, emission reduction and circularity. 	
Details of the Practice – Main steps & activities	<p>- What is the issue/topic addressed and the context which triggered the introduction of the practice for DECISO partners/promoters?</p> <p><i>PROFI Umwelt and PROFi Umwelt Transfer are funding schemes run by the city's investment and funding bank. Responsible for the programmes is BUKEA (Authority for the Environment, Climate, Energy and Agriculture).</i></p> <p><i>PROFI Umwelt Transfer was established by BUKEA as a sub-programme within the PROFi programme to support projects with a focus on resource efficiency and circular economy. Unlike other PROFi sub-programmes, PROFi Umwelt does not only target SMEs. The programme is funded by the Hamburg Climate Plan.</i></p> <p>- How does the practice reach its objectives and how it is/was implemented?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Criteria for funding are applied (focus on circularity) Supporting local economies 	

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promoting innovations through funding cooperations between enterprises and research institutions • Funding for staff, material, patent application and external services • Funding rate depends on size of the business and type of action, usually between 25% and 55%; research institutions get 100%, their share of the project should be min. 10% and not more than 40%. • Submission of project outline, consulting through IFB; funding is only possible if project has not started. <p>- <i>Who are the main stakeholders and beneficiaries of the practice?</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hamburg-based enterprises (If the project has a special significance for Hamburg, partners from outside of Hamburg can also be funded.)
<p>Resources needed for the Practice</p>	<p>N/a</p>
<p>Evidence of success (Measurable results achieved)</p>	<p>Since the launch of PROFi Umwelt (Transfer), 24 projects with a total volume of EUR 13M have been financed.</p> <p>In 2023, there will be an evaluation of the city’s investment and funding bank’s innovation support programmes as a whole, which will also include PROFi Umwelt Transfer.</p> <p>The funded projects cover a very wide range of topics: alternative materials, 3D printing, predictive maintenance, ... Unfortunately, there are not much information about the funded projects available since they are very innovative and confidential but there will be a publication of a completed project in autumn 2023 by BUKEA (https://www.ifbhh.de/api/services/document/950).</p>
<p>What worked well or not?</p>	<p>The evaluation of CO2 savings or other measurement instruments for the environmental success of the programme is not requested when applying for funding. Even after the end of the project, this has not yet been evaluated.</p> <p>However, the tool “ESTEM” is currently being developed for this purpose, with which the COs savings can also be recorded for complex projects: https://www.ressource-deutschland.de/service/estem/</p> <p>Within PROFi Umwelt, a new instrument was tested in 2021: Green Potential Screening (GPS). There have been 2 such calls so far, and there will be another in 2023/2024. This instrument is very well accepted and there are first R&D project proposals in preparation resulting from GPS projects.</p>
<p>Transfer Potential – Replicability</p>	<p>Funding schemes per se are replicable; however, one or the other criteria for funding might have to be adapted to national</p>

	requirements (according to legal framework) and may need to be sharpened in order to target circular economy.
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Table 4: Detailed description of GP2. Circular Cities (past programme) - ClimAccelerator (EIT Climate-KIC)

1. Author contact information		
Full Name	Stephanie Keßler	
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Telephone	-	
2. Organisation providing the Description		
Country	Germany	
Region	Hamburg	
Website	www.hamburg.de	
3. Public or private body responsible of the Practice		
Name of the organisation being the main public or private body in charge of this practice	Luvent Consulting GmbH (Germany) Trinity College Dublin (Ireland) Technical University of Denmark (Denmark)	
Location of the responsible public or private body:	Country	
	Region/City	
4. Good Practice general information		
Title of the Practice	Circular Cities (past programme) ClimAccelerator (EIT Climate-KIC)	
Web link	https://www.circular-cities.com/	
Timescale (start/end month/year)	Open call: February 2022 (Several steps of the programme between April and November) Demo day: December 2022	
Name the project where this practice come is coming from	n/a	
Name the project acronym	n/a	
Thematic objective of the Practice	Circular Cities programme aimed at accelerating advanced start-up teams with innovative solutions fostering the circular economy in urban areas.	
Geographical scope of the Practice	Local/ Regional / National / International European	
Location of the Practice	Country	n/a
	Region/City	n/a
5. Good Practice elements		
Abstract of the Practice	Circular Cities offered grants for start-ups combined with a tailor-made accelerator programme with circular focus and climate impact. Five thematic areas: Textiles, food, tourism, mobility, and construction	
Details of the Practice – Main steps & activities	<i>What is the issue/topic addressed and the context which triggered the introduction of the practice for DECISO partners/promoters?</i>	

	<p>A European-wide funding scheme Focus on cities. Connecting start-ups with climate-focused community, investors, partner cities, corporates, and ecosystem partners</p> <p>How does the practice reach its objectives and how it is/was implemented? Acceleration programme Stage 1 Business model development Stage 2 Validation and Traction Stage 3 Investment Readiness</p> <p>Who are the main stakeholders and beneficiaries of the practice? Start-ups with solutions that are addressing one of the main circular thematic pillars (circular mobility, food, construction, textile, tourism, electronics), or it is focusing on any other relevant area for the cities circular transition. Digitalisation services that enable circular transformation are also key sector for the programme.</p>
<p>Resources needed for the Practice</p>	<p>N/a</p>
<p>Evidence of success (Measurable results achieved)</p>	<p>On the European stage, the initial pilot in 2021 was successful: 15 start-ups were selected and 10 of those made it through the second stage of the accelerator where they benefitted from additional financial support as well as coaching, mentoring and peer-to-peer learning opportunities from industry experts and city officials. Twenty-eight of the most innovative start-ups operating in the circular economy have entered the 2022 incubation programme. With solutions covering key areas, such as mobility, construction and the built environment, textile, food, logistics, among others, the start-ups will develop their business ideas to accelerate the net-zero transition in cities.</p>
<p>What worked well or not?</p>	<p>In Hamburg, the programme was not pursued further. One reason was that there is a similar programme, the Innovations Starter of the Hamburg Investment and Funding Bank, which primarily supports start-ups in Hamburg.</p>
<p>Transfer Potential – Replicability</p>	<p>In case of Circular Cities, the combination of an accelerator programme and funding is something that might be suitable for transfer.</p>

Table 5: Detailed description of GP3. BNW circular hubs

1. Author contact information	
<p>Full Name</p>	<p>Sabine Herrmann</p>
<p>E-mail</p>	<p>sabine.herrmann1@sk.hamburg.de</p>
<p>Telephone</p>	<p>-</p>

2. Organisation providing the Description		
Country	Germany	
Region	Hamburg	
Website	www.hamburg.de	
3. Public or private body responsible of the Practice		
Name of the organisation being the main public or private body in charge of this practice	Bundesverband Nachhaltige Wirtschaft e.V. (BNW) [German Sustainable Business Association] Funded by Deutsche Bundesstiftung Umwelt (DBU) [German Federal Environmental Foundation]	
Location of the responsible public or private body:	Country	Germany
	Region/City	Berlin
4. Good Practice general information		
Title of the Practice	BNW circular hubs	
Web link	https://circularhubs.de/	
Timescale (start/end month/year)	03/2022 – 02/2024	
Name the project where this practice come is coming from	Funding initiative DBUcirconomy	
Name the project acronym	N/a	
Thematic objective of the Practice	Development of decentralized learning sites and venues for circular economy. These regional networks become contact points for knowledge exchange and cooperation for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs).	
Geographical scope of the Practice	Local/ Regional / National There are 4 circular hubs in Germany: north, east, south, west. The contact point for the regional circular hub north is based in Hamburg https://circularhubs.de/mit-uns-wirken/ .	
Location of the Practice	Country	Germany
	Region/City	Hamburg, Berlin, Wuppertal (west), Stuttgart (south), Leipzig (east)
5. Good Practice elements		
Abstract of the Practice	Support of SMEs in the development of post-fossil, circular products and services Exchange of knowledge and cooperation between SMEs should initiate new projects and enable the up-scaling of existing models, ideas and projects	
Details of the Practice – Main steps & activities	<i>What is the issue/topic addressed and the context which triggered the introduction of the practice for DECISO partners/promoters?</i> With four "Circular Hubs" distributed across Germany, learning locations for intelligent circular economy are being created for SMEs, where circular economy can be experienced in practice. In the hubs, the companies receive input and sufficient space to exchange ideas across sectors. Overall, active networks of strong SMEs, cleantech start-ups and larger companies are to be created. Together, they	

	<p>develop post-fossil, resource-efficient models and solutions that can be implemented quickly. The Circular Hubs serve as a platform for knowledge transfer, exchange of best practices (circular products), competence development and networking (companies, politics, civil society and the public sector).</p> <p>How does the practice reach its objectives and how it is/was implemented?</p> <p>Through cross-sector networking Exchange and innovation spaces for SMEs Support for SMEs undergoing circular transformation in Hamburg: Synergies are generated through the cooperation between the BUKEA (Authority for the Environment, Climate, Energy and Agriculture) and the Impact Hub Hamburg BUKEA serves as a contact point for SMEs via the “Umweltpartnerschaft” (environmental partnership) The environmental partnership is a network of more than 1,000 Hamburg-based companies that voluntarily implement environmental and climate protection measures. Impact Hub Hamburg offers space for networking, workshops etc. and a contact point to innovative ideas in the start-up scene in Hamburg</p> <p>Who are the main stakeholders and beneficiaries of the practice?</p> <p>SMEs (Hamburg-based/North Germany-based)</p>
<p>Resources needed for the Practice</p>	<p>N/a</p>
<p>Evidence of success (measurable results achieved)</p>	<p>The Circular Hub has created a circular map where CE networks and companies offering circular solutions can be found. Events of the four regions are bundled and jointly advertised and published. Best practice examples will soon be published on the website.</p>
<p>What worked well or not?</p>	<p>There is great interest in joining forces and creating a stable network for CE in Hamburg. It is therefore advantageous that in Hamburg, BUKEA and the Impact Hub, a municipal partner and a partner from the innovative start-up scene coordinate the network in Hamburg and together form the contact point. The fact that the people involved in the circular hub are still involved in many other work processes is not ideal. For establishing the network with more speed, more persons would be needed. Also, it has not yet been clarified how the project can continue to be financed after the end of the funding.</p>
<p>Transfer Potential – Replicability</p>	<p>The replicability of the circular hubs is high. It needs a foundation or association to be funded and contact points in each region. The contact points should not only be virtual but should provide rooms for</p>

	networking, workshops etc. It depends on the partners in the region how successful the hub is established amongst the local SMEs.
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Table 6 Detailed description of GP4. IFB Innovationsstarter

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2. Organisation providing the Description		
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Region	Hamburg	
Website	www.hamburg.de	
3. Public or private body responsible of the Practice		
Name of the organisation being the main public or private body in charge of this practice	IFB Hamburg – Investment and Funding Bank of Hamburg (public-law institution) and IFB Innovationsstarter GmbH (limited liability company, affiliated company of IFB)	
Location of the responsible public or private body:	Country	Germany
	Region/City	Hamburg
4. Good Practice general information		
Title of the Practice	IFB Innovations starter (IFB Innovationsstarter)	
Web link	https://innovationsstarter.com/	
Timescale (start/end month/year)	Since 2013	
Name the project where this practice come is coming from	n/a	
Name the project acronym	n/a	
Thematic objective of the Practice	To financially support promising companies and strengthen the local start-up scene, IFB Innovationsstarter GmbH promotes technology-oriented start-ups and young, innovative companies in Hamburg. Its offering includes InnoFounder, InnoRampUp and the Innovationsstarter Fonds Hamburg, three complementary programmes that support and finance promising start-ups across sectors. The Hamburg Investors Network also builds bridges between founders and investors.	
Geographical scope of the Practice	Local/ Regional (National/international)	
Location of the Practice	Country	Germany
	Region/City	Hamburg
5. Good Practice elements		
Abstract of the Practice	Supporting Hamburg start-ups in the founding phase with grants to strengthen the local start-up scene and help build promising companies. Focus on Impact Startups (start-ups pursuing the SDGs)	

<p>Details of the Practice – Main steps & activities</p>	<p><i>What is the issue/topic addressed and the context which triggered the introduction of the practice for DECISO partners/promoters?</i></p> <p>In the programme InnoFounder, funding is provided in particular, for novel, digital start-up projects, e.g., from the media and content sector.</p> <p>In the programme InnoRampUp, technological innovations from all sectors are supported. The portfolio includes, for example, start-ups from the fields of artificial intelligence (AI), life science, electric vehicles (EV), 3D printing or digital healthcare.</p> <p>In both programmes, impact start-ups are especially encouraged to apply for funding. This includes i.e., circular economy, climate change and adaptation, resource efficiency.</p> <p><i>How does the practice reach its objectives and how it is/was implemented?</i></p> <p>The programme InnoFounder, supports founders and founding teams in the pre-seed and seed phase with a flat-rate personal grant to finance living expenses and costs associated with the start-up project of up to €75,000. Funding is available for innovative start-ups in all sectors.</p> <p>The programme InnoRampUp, supports technologically highly innovative start-ups in the start-up phase with grants of up to €150,000.</p> <p><i>Who are the main stakeholders and beneficiaries of the practice?</i></p> <p>Start-ups in Pre-Seed- or Seed-Phase.</p>
<p>Resources needed for the Practice</p>	<p>n/a</p>
<p>Evidence of success (measurable results achieved)</p>	<p>In InnoRampUp, the funding volume since 2013 is €22M with 161 funded teams and appr. 16 funded start-ups per year.</p> <p>Examples for funded CE projects are: https://www.holy-technologies.com/ (recyclable carbon fiber technology) or https://www.traceless.eu/ (biocircular materials)</p> <p>In InnoFounder, the funding volume since 2018 is €6,5M with 91 funded teams and appr. 24 funded start-ups per year.</p> <p>Examples for funded CE projects are: https://www.cirplus.com/en (procurement software for recycled) or https://www.yook.one/ (product carbon footprint software)</p>
<p>What worked well or not?</p>	<p>Since the founding of the company IFB Innovationsstarter GmbH in 2013, the number of employees has increased from 1 to currently 24. This funding instrument is particularly attractive for start-ups because the funding does not have to be repaid. There is still a need for expansion with regard to CE start-ups. In the meantime, however, the</p>

	share of impact start-ups is growing. One focus of the company is also on promoting women-led start-ups, which is very well received.
Transfer Potential – Replicability	Funding schemes per se are replicable; however, one or the other criteria for funding might have to be adapted to national requirements (according to legal framework) and may need to be sharpened in order to target circular economy.

Table 7: Detailed description of GP5. Circularinvest

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Name of the organisation being the main public or private body in charge of this practice	Consortium of circularinvest: INOVA+, META, ICLEI EURO, Circle Economy
Location of the responsible public or private body:	Country various
	Region/City various
4. Good Practice general information	
Title of the Practice	Circularinvest
Web link	https://www.circularinvest.eu/
Timescale (start/end month/year)	11/2022 – 10/2026
Name the project where this practice come is coming from	Circular Cities and Regions Initiative
Name the project acronym	CCRI
Thematic objective of the Practice	CircularInvest is a project that aims to provide project development assistance (PDA) to selected circular economy (CE) project promoters from across Europe to access the resources needed to develop significant CE investment projects at local and regional scale and to close the investments during the action. In the proposal phase, CircularInvest collected signed support letters from European cities that wish to benefit from the CircularInvest PDA services with an overall investment volume exceeding €20M.
Geographical scope of the Practice	Local/ Regional/National/European
Location of the Practice	Country Europe
	Region/City various
5. Good Practice elements	

<p>Abstract of the Practice</p>	<p>supporting project promoters by providing the support they need to develop investment-ready circular economy projects at local and regional scale. Providing PDA for CE projects with a network of experts in multiple fields</p>
<p>Details of the Practice – Main steps & activities</p>	<p><i>What is the issue/topic addressed and the context which triggered the introduction of the practice for DECISO partners/promoters?</i></p> <p>CircularInvest will help cities and regions put circular strategies into action by removing obstacles and closing the gap between circular economy project promoters and investors.</p> <p><i>How does the practice reach its objectives and how it is/was implemented?</i></p> <p>Services provided by CircularInvest are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Circularity Optimisation Fundraising Business Plan Development <p><i>Who are the main stakeholders and beneficiaries of the practice?</i></p> <p>Private and public promoters of circular economy projects with proven local and regional impact. Eligible candidates include, but are not limited to, local and regional governments, associations of local municipalities, utility companies, waste management organisations, local and regional associations, and private companies.</p>
<p>Resources needed for the Practice</p>	<p>PDA service is free of charge</p>
<p>Evidence of success (Measurable results achieved)</p>	<p>Since now, there was only one call closed. In this pilot call, more than 90 CE projects were interested in getting PDA via CircularInvest. From the many applicants, one project will be chosen to provide PDA within a period of 6 to 9 months. The high number of interested persons shows the relevance of the topic. The next call will probably be launched in October and be closed at the end of the year 2023.</p>
<p>What worked well or not?</p>	<p>As the project is very new, not much can be said about it yet. The high number of interested people can be seen as positive. However, not all interested people have sent in an application. The reasons for this still need to be evaluated. It worked well that the project has only little limitations regarding the eligibility of the projects applying for PDA. So, applications came from a broad range of sectors etc.</p>
<p>Transfer Potential – Replicability</p>	<p>High, but funding and the consortium with a broad network of investors etc. need to be found.</p>

4.2. Opportunities of the Good Practices at the European & National Level.

The aforementioned detailed description of Good Practices for Pilot 1 shows that **GP 1: PROFI Environment and PROFI Environment Transfer, GP3: BNW circular hubs, GP4: IFB Innovations starters and GP5: circularinvest** (Tables 3, 5, 6, and 7, respectively) have a strong transfer potential. For this reason, replication for each one of them is considered as an opportunity not only for the organization, but also for other interested in the topic organizations at National and European level.

As far as the **GP2: Circular Cities - ClimAccelerator** (Table 4) is concerned, this could be an opportunity as long as a combination of an accelerator programme and funding are possible.

Finally, all funding criteria for all the five GPs related to Pilot 1, must be adapted to national requirements.

5. Detailed description of Good Practices and Opportunities for Pilot 2. Alentejo

5.1. Detailed description of Good Practices

The Good Practices related to Pilot 2, are presented in detail in the following Tables.

Table 8: Detailed description of GP6. URSA Project - Alqueva By-Products Recirculation Units

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Name of the organisation being the main public or private body in charge of this practice	EDIA - Empresa De Desenvolvimento e Infraestruturas do Alqueva (Alqueva Infrastructure and Development Company).	
Location of the responsible public or private body:	Country	Portugal
	Region/City	Alentejo region
4. Good Practice general information		
Title of the Practice	URSA Project - Alqueva By-Products Recirculation Units	
Web link	https://www.edia.pt/ursa/index.html	
Timescale (start/end month/year)	ongoing	
Name the project where this practice is coming from	Project financed by national program - National Environmental fund.	
Name the project acronym	URSA Project - Alqueva By-Products Recirculation Units	
Thematic objective of the Practice	Circular economy - Circular Farming	
Geographical scope of the Practice	Regional	
Location of the Practice	Country	Portugal

	Region/City	Alentejo
5. Good Practice elements		
Abstract of the Practice	<p>The promotion of soil fertility and the efficient use of irrigation water are basic principles of EDIA in the context of the environmentally sustainable management of Alqueva irrigation. The valorisation of organic by-products from agriculture and their return to the soil presents itself as the strongest and longest lasting possibility to recover soil quality, protect water and promote the efficient use of resources.</p>	
Details of the Practice – Main steps & activities	<p><i>What is the issue/topic addressed and the context which triggered the introduction of the practice for DECISO partners/promoters?</i></p> <p>Some soils although deep, are poor in organic matter, reducing its capacity to retain water and nutrients, making the soil gradually more susceptible to erosion and desertification. Intense agricultural activity in areas of degraded soils results in the degradation of downstream water bodies, namely as a result of the entry of sediments and nutrients.</p> <p>A project like URSA presents as major topic circular farming, it can be an example since it presents itself as a truly integrated strategy for promoting circular practices that covers the entire agricultural and agro-industrial sector, starting with producers, promoting the existence of proximity solutions that enable the recirculation of nutrients and the reduction of new imports, passing through the processes of disposal of by-products. This will culminate in a significant contribution to improving the quality of soil and water with concrete effects on increasing efficiency in the use of these resources and the adaptation of a region to the challenges imposed by climate change.</p> <p>In this context, the URSA project aims to develop an innovative regional approach, in a sector that is receptive to change, evident in the great transformation from rainfed to irrigated land observed in the Alentejo as a result of the possibilities made possible by the State's effort to provide water for agriculture in a vast area of southern Portugal.</p> <p><i>How does the practice reach its objectives and how it is/was implemented?</i></p> <p>The URSA Project - Alqueva By-Products Recirculation Units, a constellation of units at the service of the irrigation territory, which produce an organic fertilizer by composting, returned to farmers by exchange with the agricultural by-products delivered, for crop fertilization, contributing to the increase of soil fertility and its rehabilitation as a filtering barrier, which promotes downstream water quality and long-term sustainability of irrigation.</p> <p>URSA Project - Alqueva By-Products Recirculation Units presents as main objectives the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rehabilitation of soils as a quality agricultural support and as a filtering barrier. 	

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Favor the efficient use of water and nutrients, reducing the global needs. • Reduction of the application of mineral fertilizers and increase of agricultural profitability. • Greater soil cohesion, with less vulnerability to erosion and desertification. • Conservative circular use of organic by products produced in EFMA. • Better water quality and less susceptibility to invasive aquatic species. • Promotion of soil life, fertility regenerator and potentiator of plant health. • Carbon sequestration in soil, as opposed to burning, with reduction of greenhouse gases. <p>Who are the main stakeholders and beneficiaries of the practice? The main beneficiaries of this project are local farmers.</p>
<p>Resources needed for the Practice</p>	<p>Project URSA relies on partnerships between EDIA and local farmers. In terms of economic resources: 250 000€ financed in 70% by the National Environmental fund.</p>
<p>Evidence of success (Measurable results achieved)</p>	<p>URSA project responds to the problem of low organic matter content in soils, which translates into a reduction in fertility and capacity to retain water and nutrients.</p> <p>For each tonne of by-products that the URSA project valorises, 100kg of mineral fertiliser (10kg of nitrogen), 100 m3 of natural gas, 28670 litres of water and 750kg of CO2 are saved.</p>
<p>What worked well or not?</p>	<p>The URSA project presents itself as a truly integrated strategy for promoting circular practices that covers the agricultural and agro-industrial sectors, starting with producers, promoting the existence of proximity solutions that enable the recirculation of nutrients, making it possible to close the cycle and, therefore, a truly circular agriculture. The project presents a good support from the community, namely from farmers and contributes to closer the collaboration with them, since the delivery of organic by-products for composting is dependent on their adhesion to the project. In this sense, the project has established ways to strengthen this adhesion, whether in direct support for the collection of by-products, whether in the supply of organic compost, or through the reduction of some production costs associated with the reduction of the environmental and water footprint.</p>
<p>Transfer Potential – Replicability</p>	<p>This project presents a structure based on an efficient use of resources, namely in the protection of soil and water, and the valorisation of waste / by-products, contributing to accelerate the transition to the circular economy, through an agriculture in line with the principles of this new paradigm. Thus, this good practice is applicable in every country and region where sustainable agriculture is a priority and where there are large irrigated agricultural areas</p>

Table 9: Detailed description of GP7. AgroPaper, a sustainable and biodegradable solution for the agricultural mulching technique

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Name of the organisation being the main public or private body in charge of this practice	Smurfit Kappa	
Location of the responsible public or private body:	Country	Spain
	Region/City	Comunidad Foral de Navarra
4. Good Practice general information		
Title of the Practice	AgroPaper, a sustainable and biodegradable solution for the agricultural mulching technique	
Web link	https://www.smurfitkappa.com/products-and-services/paper-and-board/agropaper	
Timescale (start/end month/year)	ongoing	
Name the project where this practice is coming from	Project financially supported by the European Union's LIFE programme.	
Name the project acronym	LIFE AGROPAPER	
Thematic objective of the Practice	Circular economy - Circular Farming	
Geographical scope of the Practice	Regional	
Location of the Practice	Country	Spain
	Region/City	Navarra
5. Good Practice elements		
Abstract of the Practice	In the management of agricultural plastic mulching is difficult to remove the complete plastic from fields, therefore small pieces end up in the soil and the surrounding areas. A new product called AgroPaper have been developed in the region of Navarra.	
Details of the Practice – Main steps & activities	<p><i>What is the issue/topic addressed and the context which triggered the introduction of the practice for DECISO partners/promoters?</i></p> <p>There is a problem in the management of agricultural plastic mulching after its use. It is difficult to remove the complete plastic from fields, therefore small pieces end up in the soil and the surrounding areas. In addition, there is an issue when valorising the agricultural plastic</p>	

	<p>mulching because it is “dirty” with high percentage of soil on it, and usually it ends up in landfills.</p> <p>A company in Navarra has developed a new product called AgroPaper that solves this problem. It is made with pine fibres that have their origin in certified wood forests of the region. This mulching has the same advantages of the plastic mulching but improves its disadvantages.</p> <p>The company uses an internal LCA tool to compare products and evaluate the environmental impacts. It shows that regarding CO2 emissions associated, Agropaper has a good performance compared to plastic.</p> <p>A certified life cycle assessment of the product is being developed in the framework of LIFE AGROPAPER project.</p> <p>How does the practice reach its objectives and how it is/was implemented?</p> <p>A Life Cycle Cost of the product was made from the farmer purchase to its final waste management. It showed that the economic price of the product is slightly higher than the plastic mulching, but it is almost compensated, from the farmer perspective, because waste collection and management costs are avoided.</p> <p>A first test of the product was carried out in different experimental farms with the support of a public organisation, INTIA-Navarre Institute of Transfer and Innovation in Agrifood sector.</p> <p>Who are the main stakeholders and beneficiaries of the practice?</p> <p>The main beneficiaries of this project are farmers.</p>
<p>Resources needed for the Practice</p>	<p>FEDER funding was used to test the product. It was necessary the collaboration with stakeholders (farmers, agricultural institute, companies) to have feedback of the product and improve its development.</p>
<p>Evidence of success (Measurable results achieved)</p>	<p>AgroPaper has the same advantages of a plastic mulching but improves its disadvantages. There is no need to manage its waste because the product is incorporated to the soil, helping to enrich and improve the quality of the soil for future crops. It has the peculiarity to withstand the sedge, a weed that plastic mulching does not control. In addition, it avoids the carbon footprint of the plastic production because the paper has a negative one because it comes from sustainable forest.</p>
<p>What worked well or not?</p>	<p>The project presents itself as a truly integrated strategy for promoting circular practices that covers the agricultural sector promoting the existence of proximity solutions that enable circular economy and that are fully compostable, manageable in a sustainable way and without waste generation.</p> <p>AgroPaper is fully compostable according to EN13432 with optimal temperature control so that it does not overheat the crop like the polythene. There are lower handling costs as the paper is fully compostable, creating organic material for the benefit of the ground.</p>

	The collaboration with INTIA allows to guarantee the performance of AgroPaper.
Transfer Potential – Replicability	<p>Environmental impact considerations of the product from its design are remarkable in this initiative. The use of renewable and sustainable raw material avoids CO2 emissions, waste generation and the exploitation of non-renewable materials.</p> <p>To improve its characteristics, the product has been developed in collaboration with public and private stakeholders from the agri-sector, evaluating its performance in different environments and stages of the chain.</p> <p>The use of an internal comparative LCA has revealed the environmental advantages of AgroPaper. This will be confirmed by the certified life cycle assessment that is currently being developed. LCC study results must be considered along with environmental benefits.</p> <p>Other entities have the opportunity to promote this alternative in the agri-food sector and at the same time protect the environment and fulfil with the European Green Deal. The introduction of the product in the measures of the Common Agricultural Policy could be appropriate.</p>

Table 10: Detailed description of GP8. AgroFossilFree

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Name of the organisation being the main public or private body in charge of this practice	AgroFossilFree
Location of the responsible public or private body:	9 countries (IR, NL, DE, DK, PL, ES, IT, BE and EL)
4. Good Practice general information	
Title of the Practice	Fossil-Energy-Free Technologies and Strategies (FEFTS)
Web link	https://www.agrofossilfree.eu/
Timescale (start/end month/year)	Ongoing
Name the project where this practice is coming from	Project was launched by the Centre for Research and Technology–Hellas (CERTH)
Name the project acronym	Fossil-Energy-Free Technologies and Strategies (FEFTS)

Thematic objective of the Practice	Circular Farming – Fossil Free
Geographical scope of the Practice	European
Location of the Practice	Europe
5. Good Practice elements	
Abstract of the Practice	<p>The main goal of is to create a framework under which critical stakeholders will cooperate to evaluate and promote the currently available FEFTS in EU agriculture.</p> <p>FEFTS refer to the tools that are required to address cleaner and more efficient energy production and use in agriculture.</p>
Details of the Practice – Main steps & activities	<p><i>What is the issue/topic addressed and the context which triggered the introduction of the practice for DECISO partners/promoters?</i></p> <p>The main goal of AgroFossilFree project is to pave the way to EU agriculture de-fossilisation by diminishing fossil energy dependence while maintaining end product yield and quality and reducing environmental impact. To achieve this goal 5 specific objectives have been identified:</p> <p>Assessment of the current energy status in EU agriculture and identification of factors affecting innovation adoption and diffusion of FEFTS.</p> <p>Identification and registration of available FEFTS from applied research results to market solutions and exploration of existing financing tools for de-fossilising activities.</p> <p>Collaboration with all relevant stakeholders in thematic groups using interactive physical and online methodologies to produce community-based ideas for fossil-energy-free strategies and technologies integration in agricultural systems in a regional and EU-basis.</p> <p>Creation of an AgEnergy online platform with all available FEFTS to be assessed by stakeholders and provision of a Decision Support Toolkit to propose interventions and financing tools.</p> <p>Creation of policy guidelines on EU, regional and national basis and communication of them to increase visibility and promote the proposed strategies and technologies in real agricultural activity in the near future.</p> <p><i>How does the practice reach its objectives and how it is/was implemented?</i></p> <p>The main direct energy consuming activities are related to soil tillage, harvesting and sowing, with on-farm diesel use being the main direct energy input accounting for around 31% of total energy inputs. Our findings suggest that almost 8% of open-field agriculture is powered by electricity, which is used mainly for irrigation, storage, and drying activities.</p> <p>For farmers interested in reducing diesel use, these include using more efficient tractor/implement combinations, switching to renewable</p>

	<p>sources for transport, adopting agricultural practices that minimize tillage and improving farm management efficiencies.</p> <p>For instance, incorporating agrivoltaics or innovative bioenergy solutions in agricultural systems - are applicable to open-field agriculture and can increase renewable energy use both in the agricultural sector and the wider economy, while also reducing farmers' dependence on fossil fuels.</p> <p>Who are the main stakeholders and beneficiaries of the practice?</p> <p>The main beneficiaries of this project are local farmers and Eu economy.</p>
<p>Resources needed for the Practice</p>	<p>In October 2020, a 3-year CSA was started that was funded by Horizon 2020 in the amount of 2 million euros. Involving 16 partners from 9 EU countries.</p>
<p>Evidence of success (Measurable results achieved)</p>	<p>1400 FEFTS solutions are available on AgEnergy platform. It is possible to browse among FEFTS about Clean Energy Supply, Energy Efficiency Improvement and Soil Carbon Sequestration, organized in the following 5 categories: Scientific paper, Research project, Commercial technology, Training material and Financing mechanism.</p>
<p>What worked well or not?</p>	<p>AgroFossilFree is based on a "Multi Actor Approach", including in the consortium not only scientists and researchers but also extension service providers, farmers' organizations and industrial partners from 9 countries (i.e., innovation "hubs"), which ensures that the end-users of FEFTS innovations are well represented. The diversity of cropping systems and agro-climatic zones covered by the innovation "hubs" is allowing the exploration and adoption and applicability of a wide range of FEFTS solutions, while capturing a wealth of needs and innovations from end-users across Europe.</p>
<p>Transfer Potential – Replicability</p>	<p>The process of collection of research projects on FEFTS in the context of AgroFossilFree brought over 100 results which have been uploaded on the AgEnergy platform and classified based on the main categories of agricultural application: Open-field, Greenhouse, Livestock farming. This number will increase further along with the planned updates of the Platform. The collected FEFTS present innovative technologies and practices for reducing fossil energy dependence of the agricultural sector. The greatest opportunities for such a reduction were identified in energy consumption of agricultural buildings and tools, as well as fuel consumption of vehicles. Among the indirect fossil energy reduction possibilities, fertilizer, and pesticide inputs together with manure management were the most popular. Stakeholders and local farmers can replicate the results by consulting AgEnergy platform to further understand the next plan fossil reducing farming.</p>

5.2. Opportunities of the Good Practices at the European & National Level.

The aforementioned detailed description of Good Practices for Pilot 2, shows that:

- **GP6: URSA Project-Alqueva By-Products Recirculation** Units (Table 8) has a strong transfer potential in every country and region where sustainable agriculture is a priority and where there are large irrigated agricultural areas.
- **GP7: AgroPaper, A sustainable and biodegradable solution for the agricultural mulching technique** (Table 9) states that other entities have the opportunity to promote this alternative in the agri-food sector and at the same time promote the use of LCA tools and the use of a specific circular, protect the environment and fulfil the requirements of the European Green Deal. The introduction of the product in the measures of the Common Agricultural Policy could be appropriate.
- **GP8: Fossil-Energy-Free Technologies Strategies (FEFTS)** (Table 10) states that the greatest opportunities for reduction of fossil energy use are identified in energy consumption of agricultural buildings and tools, as well as fuel consumption of vehicles.

6. Detailed description of Good Practices and Opportunities for Pilot 3. NORTHWESTERN GERMANY

6.1. Detailed description of Good Practices

The Good Practices related to Pilot 3, are presented in detail in the following Tables 11-14.

Table 11: Detailed description of GP9. Rainwater treatment for industrial uses

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Location of the responsible public or private body:	Country	Germany
	Region/City	Organisation A: North-Rhine Westphalia, Nottuln Organisation B: Baden-Wuerttemberg, Haslach
4. Good Practice general information		
Title of the Practice	Rainwater Treatment Systems	
Web link	A: https://momentum-magazin.de/de/alles-fliest-betonwerk-in-nottuln-nutzt-regenwasser/ B: https://www.ingenieurbau-online.de/fachartikel/artikeldetail/nach-ueberflutungen-durch-starkregen-kontinuierlich-regenwasser-nutzen-im-gartencenter	
Timescale	A: since 2013	

(start/end month/year)	B: since 2019	
Name the project where this practice come is coming from	N. a.	
Name the project acronym	N. a.	
Thematic objective of the Practice	Collecting, storing, and treating rainwater from roof surfaces of industrial plants and other buildings to enable its use in industrial and commercial processes	
Geographical scope of the Practice	Local	
Location of the Practice	Country	Germany
	Region/City	A: North-Rhine Westphalia, Nottuln B: Baden-Wuerttemberg, Haslach
5. Good Practice elements		
Abstract of the Practice	<p>The practice is based on two specific case studies for rainwater treatment in an industrial/commercial context:</p> <p>Concrete plant that collects, stores, and treats rainwater for reuse in its production processes (case study A). a garden centre that collects, stores, and treats rainwater for irrigation of its plants (case study B).</p>	
Details of the Practice – Main steps & activities	<p><i>What is the issue/topic addressed and the context which triggered the introduction of the practice for DECISO partners/promoters?</i></p> <p>The concrete plant implemented the rainwater treatment system to save fees and operating costs in three different ways: Instead of drinking water, the rainwater that accumulates free of charge from the roof surfaces is used. If the precipitation temporarily stored in the underground cistern is sufficient, the fee-share for the otherwise required drinking water is saved. The third savings effect comes from a reduction in the precipitation fee. Agricultural and horticultural businesses are granted permission under water law to withdraw groundwater free of charge for the irrigation of their crops if this does not jeopardise the provision of drinking water in the region. The garden centre in Haslach/Kinzigtal also has such a permit for its production operation. Nevertheless, after flooding due to heavy rain, massive investments were made in rainwater storage tanks.</p> <p><i>How does the practice reach its objectives and how it is/was implemented?</i></p> <p>Both companies had to make investments first.</p> <p>The Mall company was able to use the rainwater storage tank and pump technology from its own production here, so that only the cost price had to be booked. A pump shaft with a submersible motor pump is in the area between the 200 m³ underground rainwater storage tank and the new production hall. This periodically takes the water required</p>	

	<p>for concrete production from the rainwater storage tank. Two mixing plants in the building are automatically supplied by the service water pipe. In the filter shaft in front of the storage tank, a cylindrical stainless steel slotted screen structure separates the inflow from the outflow towards the storage tank. Suspended matter that cannot pass through this filter sinks to the bottom as fine particles or floats to the water surface, such as pollen. The filter shaft can be cleared of the filter material without great effort during maintenance measures. If the rainwater reservoir in the underground storage tank is completely filled and rainwater still accumulates, the overflow from the storage tank and filter may be discharged into the public sewer without charge.</p> <p>The requirement of the building authorities to infiltrate all precipitation from the roofs of the greenhouses was already implemented. But the garden centre carried out farm extensions in 2004 and 2019, and with this last building permit, an additional retention volume was required. Therefore, a local building contractor was commissioned to work out and compare different solutions. In the end, the additional costs of the realised storage facility for the use of rainwater with infiltration of the overflow amounted to only about 10,000 euros compared to a pure retention and infiltration trench as required by the building permit. Every cubic metre of rainwater used for irrigation increases the retention potential of the entire system and thus improves heavy rainfall prevention.</p> <p>Who are the main stakeholders and beneficiaries of the practice? Case study A: concrete plant Case study B: garden centre</p>
<p>Resources needed for the Practice</p>	<p>rainwater storage tank pipe system and pumping technology filter system/sedimentation shifts (irrigation system able to cope with reuse water)</p>
<p>Evidence of success (Measurable results achieved)</p>	<p>The concrete company in Nottuln would have to pay a fee of 0.49 €/m² per square metre connected to the sewer since 01.01.2011. Since the cistern holds 200 m³, according to the drainage statutes 200 x 25 m² = 5,000 m² could be deducted from the actual collection area of 2,730 m². The result is negative, so the fee is completely waived for this section of the roof. Without rainwater storage, but with a sewer connection, it would have amounted to € 1,338 and is now saved year after year.</p> <p>For the garden centre, the rainwater management system serves as buffer for heavy rainfall. Besides, using rainwater reduces electric pumping for groundwater abstraction, has better quality than well</p>

	water, and reduces groundwater abstraction for the sake of the environment.
What worked well or not?	<p>The cement plant was able to use the rainwater storage tank and pump technology from its own production, so that only the cost price was to be booked.</p> <p>For the garden centre it is important that the water level in the well water storage tank must be adjusted to the weather conditions. This can be regulated via smartphone. The upcoming need for irrigation and the current rainwater supply are decisive for this and data from the company's own weather can be used for this.</p> <p>Issues for the system can be expected from heavy pollen drift coming from the conifers of the surrounding Black Forest. Usual rain filters are less suitable for this; therefore, sedimentation chambers are used in this case.</p>
Transfer Potential – Replicability	Both case studies are examples of successful rainwater reuse for industrial purposes. Both companies have implemented smart solutions with low treatment and land demand for storage. As almost every industrial plant has large roof areas for rainwater collection and some area on its company site the transfer potential of both approaches is very high. However, a specific approach for each company's site is needed, taking into consideration its special characteristics.

Table 12: Detailed description of GP10. Promoting the Sustainable Management of our Environment

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Location of the responsible public or private body:	Country	Germany
	Region/City	Hamburg/Hamburg
4. Good Practice general information		
Title of the Practice	SAWA's Climate Resilience Framework	
Web link	https://keep.eu/projects/6422/Strategic-Alliance-for-integ-EN/	
Timescale (start/end month/year)	31 May 2008 – 30 Dec 2011	

Name the project where this practice come is coming from	Strategic Alliance for integrated Water Management Actions	
Name the project acronym	SAWA	
Thematic objective of the Practice	<p>To improve, facilitate and accelerate the implementation of the European Flood Directive by developing a common planning and implementation strategy based on experience from a number of cases in the North Sea Region.</p> <p>To work out a decision strategy on how to use and prioritise new adaptive measures in Flood Risk Management Plans closely coordinated with the European Union Water Framework Directive implementation process to show synergetic potentials.</p> <p>To develop and compile new adaptive structural and non-structural flood mitigation measures and schemes to improve sustainable water management systems in the North Sea Region; and to prepare institutional, expert and public structures for an optimal implementation and operational capability of the Flood Directive in coordination with Water Framework Directive, focusing on education, communication, capacity building and adaptive water system measures.</p>	
Geographical scope of the Practice	International (North Sea Region)	
Location of the Practice	Country	Great Britain, Norway, Sweden, Germany and The Netherlands
	Region/City	Scotland, Norway, Southern Sweden, Hamburg, Lower Saxony and The Netherlands
5. Good Practice elements		
Abstract of the Practice	SAWA supported the implementation of the Flood Directive. The aim was to adapt water systems to the effects of climate change, focusing on sustainable development of society and regional economies. The practices associated such as the development of the sustainable flood retention basin concept addressed also circular economy challenges.	
Details of the Practice – Main steps & activities	<p><i>What is the issue/topic addressed and the context which triggered the introduction of the practice for DECISO partners/promoters?</i></p> <p>Based on case studies and pilot implementations, SAWA tested new and innovative strategies in Flood Risk Management around the North Sea. Very relevant for the OOWV are research outcomes centred around stormwater management and rainwater harvesting. The lessons learned from the challenges in adaptation of sustainable retention basins should be of benefit to all DECISO partners, particularly those of Northern Europe.</p> <p><i>How does the practice reach its objectives and how it is/was implemented?</i></p> <p>Most SAWA partners had little influence over the actual implementation of the new Flood Directive on government level. However, they proposed diverse planning and implementation</p>	

	<p>strategies that were considered by authorities. Several decision-making strategies on how to use and prioritise new adaptive measures in Flood Risk Management Plans were provided.</p> <p>New adaptive structural and non-structural flood mitigation measures and schemes to improve water management systems were introduced. Many partners focused on education, communication, stakeholder engagement, capacity building and adaptive measures. The practice had support from the relevant national, regional and local authorities and regional organisations, particularly in Norway, Sweden, Germany and The Netherlands.</p> <p>Who are the main stakeholders and beneficiaries of the practice?</p> <p>The practice involved very good collaboration between several core stakeholders and community members. The project SAWA integrated local, regional and national stakeholders, university and vocational training students. Thus, the project included a broad capacity building process incorporating information, education, and qualification.</p>
<p>Resources needed for the Practice</p>	<p>Financial resources for infrastructure alterations and public engagement activities were required.</p>
<p>Evidence of success (Measurable results achieved)</p>	<p>The measurable results achieved were as follows:</p> <p>Centres for education towards sustainable flood risk management around the North Sea.</p> <p>Adaptive strategy for implementation of Flood Risk Management Plans in the North Sea Region.</p> <p>Decision support database for flood protection measures in the North Sea Region.</p> <p>Successful implementation of sustainable water management measures with circular economy potential.</p> <p>MSc/postgraduate course on flood risk management.</p> <p>Cost-benefit analyses of measures in relation to adaptive planning strategies to optimize the implementation of Flood Risk Management Plans and River Basin Management Plans.</p>
<p>What worked well or not?</p>	<p>The following practice examples worked very well:</p> <p>Education provision both in action and writing towards sustainable flood risk management.</p> <p>Adaptive strategy for implementation of flood risk control.</p> <p>Decision support database for flood protection measures.</p> <p>Cost-benefit analyses of measures in relation to adaptive planning strategies</p> <p>Practice results such as the sustainable flood retention basin concept are easy to find, because they have been demonstrated and published.</p> <p>Sustainable drainage system applications like rain gardens.</p> <p>Some barriers were identified:</p> <p>Initial costs to establish change in practice.</p> <p>Supply chain challenges linked to specific technologies and measures that are not seen as standard.</p>

	In rare cases, technical gaps associated with quality assurance.
Transfer Potential – Replicability	<p>The practice could be replicable elsewhere due to its strong transfer options. Considerable practical transfer potential for the OOWV are particularly the outcomes of both Scottish and some Norwegian partners with respect to the sustainable flood retention basin concept and innovative sustainable drainage systems in terms of stormwater and more general rainwater recycle potential.</p> <p>The OOWV will benefit from the provision of about 40 variables used to rapidly assess water bodies including water retention basins in terms of their flood and diffuse pollution control purposes and potentials as well as rainwater harvest and recycling opportunities. The variables describe adaptive structural measures well-integrated within the landscape promoting best management practice as part of a sustainable water management strategy. The variables engineered, outlet arrangement, aquatic animal passage, land animal passage, basin and channel connectivity, seasonal influence, relative total pollution, and flotsam cover are novel. The list includes also sum parameters such as relative total pollution, which address as part of a simplified methodology several complex environmental processes.</p> <p>The sustainable flood retention basin concept also allows for the categorisation of retention areas according to bias and purposes, which is important for the OOWV when performing a cost-benefit analysis: water supply for houses and small businesses; water supply for agriculture; water supply for public authorities, production industry (excluding agriculture); sustainable drainage; environmental protection (including groundwater infiltration); recreational benefits; and landscape aesthetics.</p>

Table 13: Detailed description of GP11. Rainwater recovery rooftop garden and aeroponic greenhouse

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Name of the organisation being the main public or private body in charge of this practice	City of Budapest	
Location of the responsible public or private body:	Country	Hungary
	Region/City	Budapest/Zugló
4. Good Practice general information		
Title of the Practice	Rooftop Garden and Greenhouse Urban Farming	

Web link	https://www.interreg-central.eu/Content.Node/CWC.html	
Timescale (start/end month/year)	2019 – 2022	
Name the project where this practice come is coming from	City Water Circles	
Name the project acronym	CWC	
Thematic objective of the Practice	<p>Climate change induced hydrological risks are making central European cities increasingly vulnerable against urban floods and at the same time make the water scarcity problem worse. Coupled with growing drinking water consumption and consequently rising amounts of wastewater to be treated, this threatens the safety of future water supplies.</p> <p>The City Water Circles - CWC project aims to help municipalities to reform outdated urban water infrastructure systems via applying a circular economy approach, which offers many economic and environmental benefits. The outputs of the project will help European cities to implement water management on their territory.</p> <p>Model strategies and pilot investments have been developed, and the knowledge base supporting professional and decision-making activities will make the technologies, financial and policy tools that can be applied in cities freely available to all stakeholders.</p>	
Geographical scope of the Practice	International (Central Europe)	
Location of the Practice	Country	Hungary, Poland, Croatia, Italy, Slovenia, Germany
	Region/City	Zugló, Bydgoszcz, Split, Turin, Maribor
5. Good Practice elements		
Abstract of the Practice	<p>The pilot demonstrates rainwater management at the building level by adopting Nature Based Solutions (NBS). Rainwater from roof surfaces is harvested to feed a rooftop garden (intensive green roof) and a greenhouse-based aeroponic cultivation system for urban food production. Excess rainwater is drained into a rain garden built at the entrance of the building to promote infiltration on site and thus close the water cycle.</p>	
Details of the Practice – Main steps & activities	<p><i>What is the issue/topic addressed and the context which triggered the introduction of the practice for DECISO partners/promoters?</i></p> <p>Heavy rainfall and the resulting problems in urban areas pose new challenges for OOWV. Lack of green spaces and high surface sealing require new approaches regarding rainwater management and rainwater utilization. The intermediate storage and use of precipitation directly on site represents an interesting possibility. The results and experiences from Turin are therefore useful for OOWV.</p> <p><i>How does the practice reach its objectives and how it is/was implemented?</i></p> <p>The pilot demonstrates rainwater management at the building level by adopting Nature Based Solutions (NBS). Rainwater from roof surfaces</p>	

	<p>is harvested to feed a rooftop garden (intensive green roof) and a greenhouse-based aeroponic cultivation system for urban food production. Excess rainwater is drained into a rain garden built at the entrance of the building to promote infiltration on site and thus close the water cycle.</p> <p>The extensive green roof and terrace design offer an additional amenity benefit for a broad public. Rainwater is fully utilised on site by the implemented measures, such that no rainwater enters the rainwater sewer. Moreover, rainwater is also used for urban farming at a small scale to show the benefits of reusing rainwater in different settings. Water recycling using rainwater and treated wastewater in the building construction sector was implemented in Maribor with demonstrably positive results. This can play a role model to other industries and sectors and encourage water recycling and reuse, where drinking water quality is not mandatory for the production process.</p> <p><i>Who are the main stakeholders and beneficiaries of the practice?</i></p> <p>The practical example targets several groups. On the one hand, urban and spatial planners are to receive new ideas and expand previous knowledge. On the other hand, however, the education and sensitization of citizens is also an important point. In principle, the implementation of such measures requires the involvement of all key players. This includes the city, the administration, the water supplier, or wastewater disposal company and, finally, the citizens.</p>
<p>Resources needed for the Practice</p>	<p>Financial Resources. Involvement of various authorities and companies. Involvement of citizens.</p>
<p>Evidence of success (measurable results achieved)</p>	<p>In addition of the pictures of the installed system and finished construction. The local water utility (SMAT) has been subcontracted by the municipality of Turin to conduct the monitoring activities on site. Flow metres and data loggers are installed to measure the amount of harvested and reused rainwater for the green roof and aeroponic system as well as the amount of backup water (drinking water) used. Water quality analysis of the harvested rainwater upstream, and rainwater in the storage tank and downstream following UV disinfection will be conducted. The monitored parameters include E. coli, enterococci, total coliforms, turbidity, pH, TSS and colour.</p> <p>Next to the Pilot specific data the project has also produced several documents that can be classed as evidence of success, e.g. Policy Recommendations, Handbook or Edutainment materials.</p>
<p>What worked well or not?</p>	<p>It was useful and enriching the possibility to work with international experts in innovative sectors. Particularly, the contribution of FBR was very valuable, since it always pushed the Municipality to go beyond the “design as usual”, being ambitious in the design purposes. On these regards, it was also very useful and inspirational to have access to</p>

	<p>international innovative experiences, through technical meetings, guidelines, etc. It was particularly useful to have the feeling that innovation was successfully implemented in other context. To this aim, the potentiality of cross fertilization of project like CWC was very valuable.</p> <p>Challenges:</p> <p>Unforeseen retrofit works in the building. Since the building was built in 1940 some technical, aesthetic, and infrastructural barriers had to be solved, which required modifications in the original design concept.</p> <p>A long procurement phase due to bureaucratic hurdles, in addition to the long time required to check and approve the financial soundness of the contracted company.</p> <p>Lack of material in the post Covid-19 period, in addition to the significant increase in material costs.</p>
Transfer Potential – Replicability	<p>In particular, the intermediate storage of precipitation, on-site infiltration and reduction of surface runoff are interesting for OOWV. The practical example shows a way to create spaces in urban areas that improve the quality of stay within the city, increase safety from flooding and promote the natural water cycle. Through many small measures, larger goals can be achieved in this way.</p>

Table 14: Detailed description of GP12. Evolving Regions

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Name of the organisation being the main public or private body in charge of this practice	TU Dortmund University, Faculty of Social Sciences	
Location of the responsible public or private body:	Country	Germany
	Region/City	North Rhine-Westphalia (DE), Gemeente Kampen (NL)
4. Good Practice general information		
Title of the Practice	Evolving Regions Collaborative Roadmapping	
Web link	https://evolvingregions.com/	
Timescale (start/end month/year)	01.07.2019 - 31.03.2023	
Name the project where this practice come is coming from	n.a.	
Name the project acronym	ER	

Thematic objective of the Practice	Climate change adaptation	
Geographical scope of the Practice	International	
Location of the Practice	Country	Germany, Netherlands
	Region/City	District of Wesel, District of Steinfurt, District of Siegen-Wittgenstein, District of Soest, Geemente Zwartewaterland, District of Minden-Lübbecke, District of Coesfeld, District of Lippe
5. Good Practice elements		
Abstract of the Practice	<p>Evolving Regions provides a framework in which a wide range of different actors join forces on the road to a climate robust future. This means taking new paths of cooperation, developing and discussing common visions of the future, and using regional climate maps and regional analyses as a basis for developing actions for adapting to the consequences of climate change.</p>	
Details of the Practice – Main steps & activities	<p><i>What is the issue/topic addressed and the context which triggered the introduction of the practice for DECISO partners/promoters?</i></p> <p>Collaborating stakeholders are uniting to pave the way towards a resilient climate future. This entails forging novel avenues of cooperation, fostering dialogue to shape shared visions of the future, and utilizing regional climate maps and analyses as a foundation for devising adaptive measures to address the impacts of climate change.</p> <p><i>How does the practice reach its objectives and how it is/was implemented?</i></p> <p>The practice achieves its objectives by involving local, regional, and supra-regional stakeholders at each stage of the roadmap process. It leverages regional knowledge and experience while relying on a robust and region-specific database. Through this method, local stakeholder networks are identified, strengthened, or newly established. The external process, facilitated by the Social Research Centre of TU Dortmund University and the German Institute of Urban Affairs, provides sustainable support, and enables planning actors in the project regions. Ultimately, the outcome of this process is a roadmap that serves as a strategic guide for regional actors to plan and implement integrated climate adaptation measures, thereby fostering the development of climate-resilient regions in the future.</p> <p>The project is funded by the EU environmental 37rogramm LIFE, with additional co-financing from the Ministry of Environment, Agriculture, Nature, and Consumer Protection in North Rhine-Westphalia. Local contact persons for Evolving Roadmapping</p>	

	<p>were funded, empowering the regions to create their respective roadmaps.</p> <p>Who are the main stakeholders and beneficiaries of the practice?</p> <p>The main stakeholders and beneficiaries of the practice are:</p> <p>Local communities and residents: They benefit from the implementation of the roadmap as it aims to create climate-resilient regions, protecting them from the consequences of climate change and ensuring a sustainable future.</p> <p>Regional authorities and governments: They play a crucial role in the implementation of the roadmap, as it involves local, regional, and supra-regional stakeholders, and they are responsible for integrating climate adaptation measures into their planning and policymaking.</p> <p>Supra-regional organizations and institutions: These entities are involved in the roadmap process and contribute to the development and implementation of climate adaptation measures that go beyond individual regions and have a broader impact.</p> <p>Environmental and climate research organizations: They may be stakeholders in the process, providing valuable expertise, regional knowledge, and data to support the development of the roadmap and the implementation of climate adaptation measures.</p>
<p>Resources needed for the Practice</p>	<p>Financial Resources. Involvement of various authorities and companies. Involvement of citizens.</p>
<p>Evidence of success (measurable results achieved)</p>	<p>At the end of the project, a roadmap is created in each region as a dynamic planning document. The results of the regional processes in Evolving Regions are collected in such a roadmap, which bundles statements about objectives, strategies, possible ways to reach the objectives as well as concrete individual measures and is made available to the regions for further work. The roadmap thus serves as a guide for regional stakeholder to strategically plan and implement integrated climate adaptation measures to achieve their own objectives. The results of the regional processes bundled in the roadmap are the basis for making the regions fit for the consequences of climate change.</p>
<p>What worked well or not?</p>	<p>There were no definitive blockers identified at the moment of the interview. However, the importance of stakeholder involvement and planning the implementation of intended results has been mentioned.</p>
<p>Transfer Potential – Replicability</p>	<p>Evolving Roadmapping Guide. Best practice/blueprint of climate adaptation plans and their implementation in rural regions. Shared information on stakeholder involvement.</p>

6.2. Opportunities of the Good Practices at the European & National Level.

The collection of exemplary practices presented within the DECISO project underscores the tremendous potential and opportunities that lie ahead in advancing circular economy initiatives and sustainable development. These practices, drawn from various contexts and regions, exhibit strong transferability potential, offering valuable insights and strategies that can be harnessed by the pilot regions and beyond.

GP9: Rainwater Treatment System (Table 11): The rainwater treatment system's success in reducing operating costs and promoting sustainable water management strategies presents an opportunity for Northwestern Germany (Case 1) to explore similar smart solutions, considering its regional capabilities and rainwater utilization potential. This practice resonates with OOWV's focus on rainwater management and resource optimization, offering a tangible path to reducing costs and enhancing sustainability.

GP10 SAWA's Climate Resilience Framework: The strategic approach of SAWA in engaging stakeholders and fostering regional collaboration offers a model that resonates with the overarching objectives of the DECISO project. Its applicability to OOWV's regional context (Case 3) lies in its capacity to facilitate climate adaptation through stakeholder involvement, data-driven decisions, and strategic planning. This practice holds the potential to empower OOWV in addressing climate challenges.

GP11 Rooftop Garden and Greenhouse Urban Farming: The Rooftop Garden and Greenhouse Urban Farming practice, demonstrated in Case 3, offers OOWV a powerful strategy. By utilizing rainwater for both irrigation and rooftop farming, it offers new opportunities. This practice showcases how circular economy principles can be applied practically, addressing both water scarcity and urban agriculture challenges. OOWV's emphasis on rainwater optimization aligns seamlessly with this adaptable practice and presenting an opportunity to leverage local resources more effectively. Its transferability potential in the OOWV pilot makes it a strategic fit for DECISO's circular economy objectives.

GP12 Evolving Regions Collaborative Roadmapping: The success of Evolving Regions in promoting collaborative efforts and region-specific adaptation strategies aligns seamlessly with the goals of the DECISO project. The practice's strong transferability potential to OOWV (Case 4) lies in its approach to stakeholder engagement, climate data utilization, and roadmap creation. By adapting this model, OOWV can enhance its climate resilience strategies and strategic planning.

Collectively, these good practices offer not only innovative solutions but also valuable roadmaps for implementation. The high level of transferability is evident in the resonance between each practice and the specific themes, capabilities, and priorities of the pilot regions. By leveraging these practices, the DECISO project can capitalize on proven strategies, fostering circular economy adoption, sustainable development, and environmental conservation. The dynamic exchange of ideas and best practices enhances the collective knowledge base and paves the way for a collaborative and impactful approach to regional development, setting a precedent for circular economy initiatives that resonate beyond the pilot regions.

7. Detailed description of Good Practices and Opportunities for Pilot 4. WESTERN MACEDONIA

7.1. Detailed description of Good Practices

The Good Practices related to Pilot 4, are presented in detail in the following Tables 15-19.

Table 15: Detailed description of GP13. TITAN Cement Group

**Funded by
the European Union**

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Name of the organisation being the main public or private body in charge of this practice	TITAN Cement Group	
Location of the responsible public or private body:	Country	Greece
	Region/City	Thessaloniki
4. Good Practice general information		
Title of the Practice	Use of alternative raw materials and fuels in cement Industry (TITAN GROUP Industry)	
Web link	www.titan.gr	
Timescale (start/end month/year)	-	
Name the project where this practice come is coming from	-	
Name the project acronym	-	
Thematic objective of the Practice	<p>Waste management plans as an integral part of the national energy and climate plans.</p> <p>The Commission's guidelines for diverting more than 90% of waste from landfills by 2035.</p> <p>CO₂ emissions reduction, since RDF/SRF use are lower than those of fossil fuels because RDF/SRF contains a significant percentage of biomass.</p> <p>Reducing dependence on conventional resources, saving energy in industry, encouraging energy recovery reducing the carbon footprint of industrial activities.</p>	
Geographical scope of the Practice	Local/ Regional / National / International	
Location of the Practice	Country	Greece
	Region/City	Thessaloniki
5. Good Practice elements		
Abstract of the Practice	<p>The core of the Titan's investment program was the thermal plant, which enabled the utilization of g waste-derived fuels, resulting in low-carbon cement.</p> <p>The increased use of lower-carbon fuels that replace non-renewable fossil fuels is a key lever towards achieving TITAN's decarbonization</p>	

	<p>targets. Co-processing contributes to the conservation of natural resources, the reduction of CO₂ emissions, and the cement industry's long-term competitiveness while it also provides a low-cost circular-economy solution to society. Biomass use also increased. Dried sewage sludge, refinery sludge, tires, solid recovered fuel/ refuse derived fuel (SRF/RDF) and agricultural waste are used to substitute conventional solid fuels in several of the Group's plants.</p> <p>New installations or upgrades to the existing infrastructure for the production of alternative fuels were completed allowing plants to reach record thermal substitution levels and contributing to local waste-management efforts.</p> <p>Fully aligned with its sustainability ambitions and commitment to the circular economy, TITAN is also diversifying into the waste management sector. A notable example is the participation in the public tenders (PPPs) for mechanical and biological waste treatment (MBT) plants in Greece, in a joint venture with TERNA Energy. MBT plants can maximize recycling, minimize landfilling and secure the availability of alternative fuels, providing a solution to the critical environmental issue of municipal solid waste (MSW).</p>
<p>Details of the Practice – Main steps & activities</p>	<p><i>What is the issue/topic addressed and the context which triggered the introduction of the practice for DECISO partners/promoters?</i></p> <p>The Titan's cement industry actively contributes towards the implementation of a circular economy model at various stages of the production process. Circular economy is promoted by the recovery of materials and energy through the use of alternative raw materials and fuels.</p> <p>The use of alternative raw materials and fuels in the production of cement is a great example with considerable benefits to address the problem of waste management. It is a critical aspect in the circular economy model, which fully promotes the reduction of waste and the reuse, repair, and recovery of materials and energy. The use of alternative raw materials contributes towards saving natural, non-renewable resources. They are mostly by-products and waste of other sectors, such as fly ash, bottom ash of thermoelectric power plants, blast furnace slag, iron lamination scales, glass recycling waste, dredging spoils, demolition waste and concrete production waste.</p> <p><i>How does the practice reach its objectives and how it is/was implemented?</i></p> <p>Titan uses recycled excess concrete and demolition waste in the production of cement, sending a clear message that buildings and concrete are recyclable. In other European countries, these materials are only used as aggregates in the construction of roads.</p> <p>Concrete returns, which would otherwise be sent to landfills, are already being used as alternative raw materials in the production of cement.</p>

	<p>Using alternative fuels, as fuel in the furnace producing clinker, the waste that would otherwise have to be buried, energy contained in them is recovered.</p> <p>Alternative fuels generally contain a high percentage of biomass, which brings about a reduction of CO₂ emissions.</p> <p>They include secondary refuse derived fuel (SRF, RDF), dried sewage sludge from waste water treatment plants, petroleum residues mixed with sawdust, used oils and lubricants, packaging recycling residues, paper, wood, sawdust, fabric, biomass from agricultural and forest residues, animal feed, and organic waste, end-of-life tyres, etc.</p> <p>Who are the main stakeholders and beneficiaries of the practice? Paper, wood, sawdust, fabric, waste management industries, municipalities</p>
Resources needed for the Practice	Titan' s own contribution
Evidence of success (Measurable results achieved)	450.000 tns of CO ₂ emissions reduction 800.000 Waste tns target to be utilized Landfill reduction 100.000 tns of fossil fuels reduction
What worked well or not?	<p>The major challenge was the successful implementation of all the necessary anti-pollutant technologies that would ensure the non-dispersion of air pollutants.</p> <p>The very good results are validated via the on-line environmental platform that has developed Titan, in order to establish free access to everyone who intends to check emissions.</p>
Transfer Potential – Replicability	This good practice is applicable in every country and region where cement industry exists.

Table 16: Detailed description of GP14. SITA Zielona Energia

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Name of the organisation being the main public or private body in charge of this practice	SITA Zielona Energia
	Country Poland

Location of the responsible public or private body:	Region/City	City of Poznan and nine surrounding municipalities
4. Good Practice general information		
Title of the Practice	Poznan Energy from Waste Plant, Poland	
Web link	https://prezero-zielonaenergia.pl	
Timescale (start/end month/year)	Tender announced on 4 April 2011, Commissioning in 2016	
Name the project where this practice come is coming from	-	
Name the project acronym	-	
Thematic objective of the Practice	<p>Energy efficiency obligation schemes and alternative policy measures. National circular economy requirements, as a core element of member states development strategy.</p> <p>Energy utilisation of residues above landfilling in hierarchy of mixed municipal waste management.</p> <p>Waste management plans as an integral part of the national energy and climate plans.</p> <p>Circular economy combined with energy sector development and environmental protection.</p> <p>EU's energy security and security of supply ensuring the strategic diversification of energy products, while at the same time modernising and developing energy infrastructures.</p> <p>Ensuring openness and innovation in order to achieve growth that will create new jobs.</p> <p>Actions for reducing emissions in the agricultural sector.</p> <p>The Commission's guidelines for diverting more than 90% of waste from landfills by 2035.</p>	
Geographical scope of the Practice	Local/ Regional / National / International	
Location of the Practice	Country	Poland
	Region/City	City of Poznan and nine surrounding municipalities
5. Good Practice elements		
Abstract of the Practice	<p>The Project consists of a waste-to-energy plant complying with the relevant national and European standards, including the EU Directive on waste incineration, for an expected contract period of 30 to 35 years, structured as an availability scheme.</p> <p>In order to comply with new national and European environmental standards on waste disposal, a number of Polish cities and regions have commenced project preparation for the construction of waste incinerators. The project is consistent with national and regional strategic documents and the objectives of the Polish Operational Programme Infrastructure and Environment (OPI&E), making them eligible for EU grant co-financing, with grant amounts reserved for their co-financing. Approximately EUR 84 million was pre-allocated to the</p>	

	<p>Project by the Polish managing authority under the relevant Priority Axis. The waste-to-energy project of the City of Poznan is one of the most advanced cases in Poland of a greenfield project attempting to combine EU funds (from the Cohesion Fund) with a PPP (public-private partnerships) structure. As the Project’s investment cost exceeds EUR 50 million, it qualifies as a “major project” under Article 39 of the Council Regulation laying down general provisions on the EU Funds and was subject to decision by the Commission.</p>
<p>Details of the Practice – Main steps & activities</p>	<p><i>What is the issue/topic addressed and the context which triggered the introduction of the practice for DECISO partners/promoters?</i></p> <p>The new energy-from-waste plant in Poznań consists of a successful technical example in the production of thermal energy from municipal solid waste. The plant is designed to convert about 216,000 tonnes of waste per year into electricity and district heat. Moreover, Adjacent to the energy from waste plant is a treatment facility that handles the bottom ash. Various fractions of aggregates as well as most of ferrous and non-ferrous materials in the bottom ash are separated for re-use.</p> <p><i>How does the practice reach its objectives and how it is/was implemented?</i></p> <p>Sita Zielona Energia, a joint venture was chosen by the city of Poznań to carry out the design, construction, financing, and operation of the plant over a period of 25 years. In its role as nominated contractor, the consortium fully supported the client until the common contract award in this first public-private-partnership project in the waste sector in Poland. The plant is located in an industrial zone in the vicinity of the city of Poznań. The process technology of the plant features the latest innovations in grate combustion for improved combustion control and makes it possible to reduce nitrogen dioxide levels to half the current EU limit. The thermal energy released by the combustion process is recovered in a four-pass boiler producing superheated steam. The carefully selected steam parameters enhance both energy efficiency and reliability of the boiler. With a thermal input from waste of two times 31.5 MW, net electrical energy of up to 15 MW and district heat of up to 34 MW can be exported. The two-line plant is designed to convert about 216,000 tonnes of waste per year into electricity and district heat for the local grid.</p> <p><i>Who are the main stakeholders and beneficiaries of the practice?</i></p> <p>Waste management industries, City of Poznan and nine surrounding municipalities, citizens, national economy, industries that make use of the produced heat. The new plant makes a great contribution to the local supply of energy.</p>
<p>Resources needed for the Practice</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public-private partnership (“PPP”) - Polish Operational Programme Infrastructure and Environment 2007-2013
<p>Evidence of success</p>	<p>216,000 waste tonnes per year Landfill reduction</p>

(Measurable results achieved)	17.6 MW (max) electric power generation 34 MW (max) district heating output 65.000 tns of bottom ash and 9.000 tns of Flue gas treatment residues are separated for re-use.
What worked well or not?	There have not been mentioned any problems
Transfer Potential – Replicability	This good practice is applicable in every country and region, since waste management, waste to energy practice and Landfill reduction are major issues that concern every EU state member.

Table 17: Detailed description of GP15. Econotre, a model for the circular economy

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Location of the responsible public or private body:	Country: France
	Region/City: Econotre Haute Garonne
4. Good Practice general information	
Title of the Practice	Econotre, a model for the circular economy
Web link	https://www.econotre.fr/
Timescale (start/end month/year)	Econotre commissioning began in January 2001.
Name the project where this practice come is coming from	Econotre
Name the project acronym	-
Thematic objective of the Practice	<p>Circular economy combined with energy sector development and environmental protection.</p> <p>Energy efficiency schemes and alternative policy measures.</p> <p>National circular economy requirements, as a core element of member states development strategy.</p> <p>Energy utilisation of residues above landfilling in hierarchy of mixed municipal waste management.</p> <p>Waste management plans as an integral part of the national energy and climate plans.</p> <p>EU's energy security and security of supply ensuring the strategic diversification of energy products, while at the same time modernising and developing energy infrastructures.</p>

	<p>Ensuring openness and innovation in order to achieve growth that will create new jobs.</p> <p>Actions for reducing emissions in the agricultural sector.</p> <p>The Commission’s guidelines for diverting more than 90% of waste from landfills by 2035.</p>
Geographical scope of the Practice	Local/ Regional / National / International
Location of the Practice	Country France
	Region/City Garonne
5. Good Practice elements	
Abstract of the Practice	<p>Econotre consists of a local circular economy hub that gathers all treatment modes in a single site: (Mechanical treatment, composting, thermal treatment, energy recovery unit).</p> <p>The Econotre heat network was built thanks to the ambition shared by Decoset, Bessières town hall and Econotre to generate alternative renewable energy to support the energy transition and local socio-economic development. Experts worked on new high-performance cogeneration technology to make it possible. The result is a first in France.</p>
Details of the Practice – Main steps & activities	<p><i>What is the issue/topic addressed and the context which triggered the introduction of the practice for DECISO partners/promoters?</i></p> <p>Econotre represents one of the most integrated European industrial tools at the service of new local energy resources and local economy development, since it includes: sorting center for recyclable household waste from selective collections, energy recovery center for household and similar waste that cannot be recycled, a bottom ash recovery center, green waste composting center. The sorting center produces secondary raw material for new plastic bottles, cans, public benches, recycled paper, egg cartons...Energy recovery with treatment of non-recyclables to produce electricity and heat. Heat for agriculture: The low-temperature energy still available after combustion has been recovered to supply heat to the vegetable greenhouses built alongside the site, rather than being dissipated in the atmosphere.</p> <p><i>How does the practice reach its objectives and how it is/was implemented?</i></p> <p>The facility uses incineration to recover the value from household waste generated by the Decoset municipalities. This processing method exploits the energy generated by burning the waste to produce electricity and heat. Econotre uses the heat released by burning the waste to produce electricity with a turbo-alternator. Low temperature steam allows to reach high levels of energy recovery.</p> <p><i>Who are the main stakeholders and beneficiaries of the practice?</i></p> <p>Citizens, municipalities, national economy, industries. The plant makes a great contribution to the local supply of energy.</p>

Resources needed for the Practice	Econotre is the industrial company chosen by the Syndicat mixte DECOSET to finance, build and operate facilities for the treatment and recovery of household and similar waste produced by 153 municipalities attached to it, within the framework of a public service delegation.
Evidence of success (Measurable results achieved)	<p>Econotre represents 30,000 tonnes of recyclable household waste sorted, 45,000 tonnes of bottom ash recovered, 8,000 tonnes of green waste recovered, and 3,500 tonnes of compost produced every year. Every year, the 10 hectares of vegetable greenhouses built alongside the Econotre centre are supplied with 25,000 MWh of thermal energy. This recovered heat supplements the 120,000 MWh of electricity already generated by Econotre (equivalent to the consumption of 21,300 homes) by burning 192,000 tonnes of waste and 45,000 tonnes of bottom ash recovered.</p> <p>The greenhouses, which will ultimately produce 6,000 tonnes of local tomatoes per year. These favourable conditions have enabled them to extend the greenhouses, which will cover 10 hectares, and create about a hundred local jobs.</p> <p>86 co-workers. 2,200 tonnes of oil equivalent saved. 6,000 tonnes of CO₂ avoided per year.</p>
What worked well or not?	There have not been mentioned any problems
Transfer Potential – Replicability	This good practice is applicable in every country and region, since waste management, waste to energy practice and Landfill reduction are major issues that concern every EU state member.

Table 18 Detailed description of GP16. Innovative Technologies for Ecological and Efficient Pyrolysis of Waste Treatment

1. Author contact information		
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2. Organisation providing the Description		
Country	Greece	
Region	Macedonia	
Website		
3. Public or private body responsible of the Practice		
Name of the organisation being the main public or private body in charge of this practice	ecoHORNET	
Location of the responsible public or private body:	Country	Romania
	Region/City	
4. Good Practice general information		
Title of the Practice	Innovative Technologies for Ecological and Efficient Pyrolysis of Waste Treatment	

Web link	https://circulareconomy.europa.eu/platform/en/good-practices/echornet-develops-multi-system-burner-ecological-combustion-procedure-create-pyrolysis-gas-oil-and-biochar	
Timescale (start/end month/year)	05/2019 - ongoing	
Name the project where this practice is coming from	N/a	
Name the project acronym	N/a	
Thematic objective of the Practice	ecoHORNET, a Romanian SME, has developed a recycling station that uses pyrolysis technology to transform industrial biomass, household waste and sewage sludge into bio-gas, bio-oil and biochar in addition to creating thermal energy for hot water and air generators.	
Geographical scope of the Practice	International	
Location of the Practice	Country	Romania
	Region/City	Chiajna
5. Good Practice elements		
Abstract of the Practice	ecoHORNET has created the W2E recycling eco station. Using pyrolysis, this machine enables creating, efficiently and without pollution, bio-based oil and gas out of everything that burns. By thermo-chemically treating industrial biomass and other non-recyclable waste in the absence of oxygen, the W2B recycling eco station creates valuable products such as recyclable pyrolysis gas, pyrolysis oil, biochar, carbon black and other biologically neutral residues, which can then be stored ecologically and used for the recovery of energy from waste.	
Details of the Practice – Main steps & activities	<p><i>What is the issue/topic addressed and the context which triggered the introduction of the practice for DECISO partners/promoters?</i></p> <p>Agri-pellets made from waste and residues from agriculture, including vegetal and animal substances, forestry and related industries, as well as the biodegradable part of industrial and municipal waste are combusted to generate energy and bio-products. The ecoHORNET company has developed and patented technologies and equipment's for Waste 2 Energy Treatment Stations with efficient, economic and ecologic production of thermal and electric energy, pyrolysis oil, biochar, pyrolysis gas using natural biomass, municipal waste and organic waste resulted from industry or human activities.</p> <p><i>How does the practice reach its objectives and how it is/was implemented?</i></p> <p>The operating costs are minimal, the installation is self-sustainable from an energetic point of view, the activity is profitable, and it does not require government subventions; the obtained products (bio gas, bio oil, biochar) are of the best quality.</p>	

	<p>Because of the high temperatures generated by the ecoHORNET burners, the pyrolysis installation allows the user to adjust the process in the range starting from 150°C and up to 900°C, according with the processed material and the desired pyrolysis end-products.</p> <p>Low temperature pyrolysis (150-450°C): 35% biochar, 50% pyrolysis oil, 15% pyrolysis gases.</p> <p>Medium temperature pyrolysis (450-650°C): 25% biochar, 30% pyrolysis oil, 45% pyrolysis gases.</p> <p>High temperature pyrolysis (650-900°C): 15% biochar, 15% pyrolysis oil, 70% pyrolysis gases.</p> <p>The estimates are from using the pyrolysis process on the following organic solid waste: agricultural, forestry, horticultural, household, etc.</p> <p>Pyrolysis oil: It is a dark-brown colored liquid. It has a chemical composition similar to that of biomass; It has a higher energetic density than the solid fuels, which reduces the storage and transport costs; It is used as industrial fuel as a replacement for oil and gasoline, and also in the chemical industry. Products obtained from the pyrolysis oil: Mixtures of chemical compounds, which can be further separated in the classical refineries; Nitrogen compounds; Crude oil; Combustible gases (primary separation) and light hydrocarbons (naphthenes, toluene etc.), phenols, methyls, aldehyde, gasoline (after refining).</p> <p>Biochar: The Biochar is porous and hygroscopic, and it is used to combat desertification, because its capacity to attract and retain water. As a results, nutrients such as nitrogen, phosphorus, and agro-chemicals are kept a longer time in soil. The plants grow healthier, and the fertilizers infiltrate less in the groundwater.</p> <p>W2B eco recycling unit has a production capacity of 2 tonnes an hour and can be used in any industrial waste recycling flow to recover valuable products such as bio-fuels and biochar. With 2 kg of pelleted agricultural waste, the W2B recycling eco unit can produce bio-fuels equivalent to 1 m3 of natural gas, 1 liter of diesel fuel, or 4 kg of wood.</p> <p>Who are the main stakeholders and beneficiaries of the practice? Small towns or villages or industrial companies, on a subscription basis, using mobile installations.</p>
<p>Resources needed for the Practice</p>	<p>DHCA already operates a plant for the combustion of a mixture of agricultural residues and lignite. In case the mixture consists of agricultural and forestry residues alone, the raw materials for fuel are available, quickly renewable and they do not produce ecologic disturbances from their collecting.</p>
<p>Evidence of success (measurable results achieved)</p>	<p>The company ecoHORNET SRL ROMANIA became ELITE MEMBER in WORLD CONFEDERATION OF BUSINESSES headquartered in HOUSTON TEXAS, UNITED STATE OF AMERICA</p>
<p>What worked well or not?</p>	<p>N/a</p>

Transfer Potential – Replicability	DHCA already operates a biomass combustion plant using a mixture of biomass- lignite. Substitution of lignite fraction with biomass (agricultural and forestry residues as well as wastes) should be considered. Combustion by products must be chemically and physically analyzed in terms of their potential to becoming secondary raw materials.
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Table 19: Detailed description of GP17. The Revised National Waste Management Plan for the period 2020-2030

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Full Name	Athina Krestou	
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2. Organisation providing the Description		
Country	Greece	
Region	-	
Website	-	
3. Public or private body responsible of the Practice		
Name of the organisation being the main public or private body in charge of this practice	Hellenic Ministry of Environment & Energy	
Location of the responsible public or private body:	Country	Greece
	Region/City	-
4. Good Practice general information		
Title of the Practice	The Revised National Waste Management Plan for the period 2020-2030	
Web link	open gov	
Timescale (start/end month/year)	From 10/2022 until 2030	
Name the project where this practice is coming from	N/a	
Name the project acronym	NWMP	
Thematic objective of the Practice	Waste Management	
Geographical scope of the Practice	National	
Location of the Practice	Country	Greece
	Region/City	Throughout the country
5. Good Practice elements		
Abstract of the Practice	The recent Waste Management legislation provides support for energy recovery from waste, including the retrofitting of Waste Treatment Units (WTPs) into Waste Recovery Units (WREUs). The energetic valorization of secondary fuels and residues is also promoted.	

Details of the Practice – Main steps & activities	<p><i>What is the issue/topic addressed and the context which triggered the introduction of the practice for DECISO partners/promoters?</i></p> <p>The GP is a legislation process to address the framework for energy recovery from waste in Greece. The legislation promotes the use of financial support from European (Just Transition) and national (Green) funds.</p> <p><i>How does the practice reach its objectives and how it is/was implemented?</i></p> <p>The GP is in progress.</p> <p><i>Who are the main stakeholders and beneficiaries of the practice?</i></p> <p>All public and private bodies in Greece possibly involved in aspects about energy recovery from waste</p>
Resources needed for the Practice	No
Evidence of success (measurable results achieved)	N/a
What worked well or not?	N/a
Transfer Potential – Replicability	The GP can facilitate the Western Macedonia regional pilot to retrofit its installations towards the use of wastes and residues as fuels for thermal energy production, thus decreasing the % of wastes that are buried in the regional landfill and at the same time increasing the energy production.

7.2. Opportunities of the Good Practices at the European & National Level.

The aforementioned, detailed description of Good Practices for Pilot 4, revealed the following opportunities:

- **GP13: Use of alternative raw materials and fuels in cement Industry** (Table 15) has strong transfer potential in every country and region where cement industry exists. For the pilot partner it is an opportunity to explore the increased use of lower-carbon fuels that could replace non-renewable fossil fuels.
- **GP14: Poznan Energy from waste Plant, Poland** (Table 16), has a strong transfer potential in every country and region. For the pilot partner it is an opportunity to learn from the operation of the new energy-from-waste plant in Poznań, that consists of a successful technical example in the production of thermal energy from municipal solid waste.
- **GP15: Econotre eco-notre** (Table 17) has also a strong transfer potential in every country and region. As far as the pilot partner is concerned, it is an opportunity to learn from the operation of the local circular economy hub that gathers all treatment modes in a single site: Mechanical treatment, composting, thermal treatment, energy recovery unit.
- **GP16: Innovative Technologies for Ecological and Efficient Pyrolysis of Waste Treatment** (Table 18) is an opportunity for the pilot partner since it already operates a biomass combustion plant using a mixture of biomass- lignite. Substitution of lignite fraction with biomass (agricultural and forestry residues as well as wastes) should be considered. Combustion by products must be chemically and physically analysed in terms of their potential to becoming secondary raw materials.
- **GP17: The Revised National Waste Management Plan for the period 2020-2030** (Table 19), is an opportunity that can facilitate the Western Macedonia regional pilot to retrofit its installations towards the

use of wastes and residues as fuels for thermal energy production, thus decreasing the % of wastes that are buried in the regional landfill and at the same time increasing the energy production.

8. Conclusions

DESICO pilot partners will use this deliverable and the conclusions following (for use of all Good Practices in the DECISO framework and focus) for the project next steps, tasks, and work packages and mostly to combine them with the ongoing D1.3 – Reports from mobilization and mutual learning workshops in the pilot areas.

8.1. Pilot 1. FREIE UND HANSESTADT HAMBURG

GP 1. PROFI Environment - PROFI Environment Transfer

Discussion - Local Relevance and Support for Hamburg:

The good practice of PROFI Umwelt offers valuable insights into a financing scheme with focus on environmental projects and ideas. As financing circular economy with focus on Hamburg-based enterprises from different sectors is one part of the GP, it can support the DECISO pilot project with the experience of establishing a framework for financial support in this field.

Support for DECISO Pilot Project:

Longstanding Expertise: The GP can support the DECISO pilot project in Hamburg by offering experiences of almost 10 years of running this financing scheme.

- **Learnings from evaluation:** The innovation support programmes of the city's investment and funding bank will be evaluated in 2023. Hamburg's DECISO pilot project can profit from the learnings of this evaluation.
- **Operational Guidance:** Understanding the regulatory framework of PROFI Umwelt can support the pilot with operational advice on how to build the programme in the pilot.
- **Stakeholder Engagement:** Experts of this GP are offering advice as stakeholders in the DECISO pilot programme.

Conclusion:

PROFI Umwelt serves as a good practice example on how to support environmental initiatives in Hamburg financially. The longstanding experience of the programme as well as its experts serving as engaged stakeholders for the pilot project can valuably support building a financial support programme for circular economy in Hamburg.

GP 2. Circular Cities - ClimAccelerator

Discussion - Local Relevance and Support for Hamburg:

Hamburg's start-up landscape is a diversified scene with enterprises on different maturity levels. The ClimAccelerator with focus on accelerating advanced start-ups offers support to those start-ups with the most innovative ideas in the field of circular economy.

Support for DECISO Pilot Project:

- **Focus sectors:** The Hamburg DECISO pilot can profit from the ClimAccelerator's focus on circular economy main sectors (mobility, food, construction, textile, tourism, electronics) as well as its strong attitude in supporting digitalisation services.
- **Financial configuration:** The combination of different financial schemes (grants and a tailor-made accelerator programme) offers insights in various configuration possibilities of the pilot project's financial framework.

- **Circular Economy Ecosystem:** The management of the different stakeholder groups (communities, investors, cities, corporates) can facilitate the pilot programme in Hamburg where many different stakeholders are involved as well.

Conclusion:

The ClimAccelerator offers valuable insights in a support programme for a certain focus group (advanced start-ups) particularly acting in main sectors of circular economy. Beside the broad approach of GP 1, the ClimAccelerator can share detailed experiences with supporting start-ups with circular economy focus, which is very relevant for Hamburg's growing start-up scene.

GP 3. BNW circular hubs

Discussion - Local Relevance and Support for Hamburg:

Circular solutions often require many actors from different sectors/areas. For example, not only material scientists but also packaging designers are needed for circular packaging solutions. The circular hub addresses this issue by developing learning sites and a regional network for exchange and cooperation of SMEs designing joint solutions.

Support for DECISO Pilot Project:

- **Circular Network:** The circular hub north offers access to a broad network of stakeholders from different backgrounds within Hamburg, whereas the other three circular hubs serve as contact points for the national network of enterprises and organizations working on circular solutions. The network and CE stakeholders are visualized on a “circular map”.
- **Knowledge transfer:** For the implementation of the pilot project, it is crucial to gain knowledge on the latest state of research and any new developments regarding circular economy. The circular hub serves as platform for this knowledge transfer.
- **Inter-institutional collaboration:** Providing track record of the collaboration between municipal partners and partners from the innovative start-up scene jointly managing the project and the large network of stakeholders.

Conclusion:

The circular hub offers the DECISO pilot project a large network with many valuable contacts to people and organisations which are intensively involved in circular economy ideas in Hamburg and the surrounding area. Furthermore, the exchange of knowledge is important not only in Hamburg, but also with the other circular hubs in Germany, to integrate the latest developments into the pilot project.

GP 4. IFB Innovations starter

Discussion - Local Relevance and Support for Hamburg:

The IFB Innovationsstarter provides valuable track record on a financing scheme offering different types of financial support to enterprises with innovative ideas in Hamburg. This is very relevant for developing the pilot programme in Hamburg since circular solutions might need various funding schemes.

Support for DECISO Pilot Project:

- **Investment Contacts:** With the Hamburg Investors Network this GP offers important contacts to a network which is matching founders of innovative enterprises with business angels and venture capital.
- **Successful implementation:** Insights from a financing scheme with more than ten years of experience and strong growth can support the implementation of the pilot programme.
- **Diversified Portfolio:** The GP facilitates knowledge transfer across a broad portfolio of funding mechanisms for businesses and ideas of circular economy at different stages of maturity.

Conclusion:

For developing the DECISO pilot programme in Hamburg, the IFB Innovationsstarter is an important GP with its deep knowledge of financing schemes and the fruitful cooperation with Hamburg’s investors scene to accumulate venture capital and gather business angels willing to invest in innovative sustainable ideas.

GP 5. Circularinvest

Discussion - Local Relevance and Support for Hamburg:

Circularinvest offers beneficial know-how in supporting cities and regions, which focus on operationalising regional circular strategies. Within this GP, Project Development Assistance (PDA) is provided for selected applicants. This can create synergies with the PDA that is being developed at DECISO pilot in Hamburg.

Support for DECISO Pilot Project:

- **Fundraising Possibilities:** Networking opportunities for the pilot project in terms of circular economy project promoters and investors.
- **PDA expertise:** Guidance on the operationalisation of PDA for circular economy ideas.
- **Europe-wide learnings:** Circularinvest provides more GP examples from other European cities and regions improving their circular economy strategies.

Conclusion:

With the solely focus on circular economy and its strong expertise in different aspects of the implementation of PDA in circular economy, Circularinvest grants useful support in matching project ideas with PDA developers and investors. The DECISO pilot in Hamburg relates to the Circularinvest team for further collaboration.

8.2. Pilot 2. ALENTEJO

GP 6. URSA Project-AlquevaBy-Products Recirculation Units

Discussion - Local Relevance and Support: For the pilot region This GP responds to the problem of low organic matter content in soils, which represents an increment of fertility and soil capacity to retain water and nutrients.

By increasing the project area, the region can truly integrated strategy for promoting circular practices that covers the agricultural and agro-industrial sectors, starting with producers, promoting the existence of proximity solutions that enable the recirculation of nutrients, making it possible to close the cycle and, therefore, a truly circular agriculture.

Support for DECISO Pilot Project: The increment of fertility and soil capacity to retain water and nutrients showcased here can offer support to the DECISO pilot project in:

- **Expertise Sharing:** Collaboration with the project entities can provide valuable insights into system design and implementation since other entities have the opportunity to promote this alternative in the agri-food sector and at the same time protect the environment and fulfil with the European Green Deal.
- **Feasibility Assessment:** Learning from the experiences of these case study can help the pilot project assess the feasibility in a regional context.
- **Stakeholder Engagement:** Engaging with specific stakeholders can facilitate dialogue and collaboration among businesses, government agencies, and local communities.
- **Technical Guidance:** Understanding the technological aspects can aid the pilot project in selecting appropriate equipment and strategies.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, this good practice example highlights how increment of fertility and soil capacity to retain water and nutrients aligns with circular economy principles and supports sustainable growth. Tailoring this practice will enable the DECISO pilot project to make informed decisions, promote circular economy practices, and contribute to the region's long-term well-being.

GP 7. AgroPaper, a sustainable and biodegradable solution for the agricultural mulching technique

Discussion - Local Relevance and Support: The project example provides insights that can benefit cleaner and more efficient management of agricultural plastic mulching after its use.

Support for DECISO Pilot Project: This experience offers direct support in the following ways:

- **Expertise Sharing:** Collaboration with the project entities can provide valuable insights into system implementation since other entities have the opportunity to promote new solutions regarding valorising the agricultural plastic mulching because it is “dirty” with high percentage of soil on it, and usually it ends up in landfills.
- **Feasibility Assessment:** Learning from the experiences of these case study can help the pilot assess the feasibility in Alentejo regional context.
- **Circular Economy Potential:** The analysis of the Life Cycle Cost of the product from the farmer purchase to its final waste management is important to show the economic benefits and the circular potential since waste collection and management costs are avoided. The use of an LCA tools to compare products and evaluate the environmental impacts allows to show new solutions. The project presents itself as a truly integrated strategy for promoting circular practices that covers the agricultural sector promoting the existence of proximity solutions that enable circular economy and that are fully compostable, manageable in a sustainable way and without waste generation.
- **Stakeholder Engagement:** Engaging with specific stakeholders can facilitate dialogue and collaboration among several stakeholders regarding the use of certified life cycle analysis and assessment.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, this good practice example will enable the DECISO pilot project to make informed decisions, promote circular economy practices, and contribute to the region's long-term well-being.

GP8. Fossil-Energy-Free Technologies and Strategies (FEFTS)

Discussion - Local Relevance and Support: The project example provides insights that can benefit cleaner and more efficient energy production and use in agriculture.

Support for DECISO Pilot Project: This experience offers direct support in the following ways:

- **Expertise Sharing:** Collaboration with the project entities can provide valuable insights into system design and implementation since other entities have the opportunity to promote Fossil-Energy-Free Technologies and Strategies.
- **Feasibility Assessment:** Learning from the experiences of these case study can help the pilot assess the feasibility in a regional context.
- **Circular Economy Potential:** Enhance EU agriculture de-fossilisation by diminishing fossil energy dependence while maintaining end product yield and quality and reducing environmental impact.
- **Stakeholder Engagement:** Understanding the collaboration and engagement strategies employed can help create a framework under which critical stakeholders will cooperate to evaluate and promote the currently available FEFTS in EU agriculture and to effectively involve relevant parties.

8.3. Pilot 3. NORTH WESTERN GERMANY

GP 9. Rainwater Treatment Systems

Discussion - Local Relevance and Support for Northwestern Germany: For the pilot region of Northwestern Germany, where the OOWV aims to explore rainwater use solutions, this good practice example offers

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valuable insights. The utilization of rainwater for industrial purposes aligns with OOWV's objective of sustainable water management. By adopting similar rainwater treatment systems, the region can:

- Reduce reliance on external water sources, optimizing resource usage.
- Mitigate water-related costs for businesses, fostering economic growth.
- Contribute to environmental conservation by decreasing groundwater abstraction.
- Enhance the region's resilience to heavy rainfall events, preventing flooding.

Support for DECISO Pilot Project: The rainwater reuse practices showcased here can offer support to the DECISO pilot project in Northwestern Germany:

- **Expertise Sharing:** Exchange with the concrete plant and garden center can provide valuable insights into system design and implementation.
- **Feasibility Assessment:** Learning from the experiences of these case studies can help the pilot project assess the feasibility of rainwater treatment systems for the local context.
- **Stakeholder Engagement:** Engaging with companies like the concrete plant and garden center can facilitate dialogue and collaboration among businesses, government agencies, and local communities.
- **Technical Guidance:** Understanding the technological aspects of rainwater treatment can aid the pilot project in selecting appropriate equipment and strategies.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, this good practice example highlights how rainwater reuse in general aligns with circular economy principles and supports sustainable growth. Tailoring this practice to the unique capabilities of Northwestern Germany will enable the DECISO pilot project to make informed decisions, promote circular economy practices.

GP 10. SAWA's Climate Resilience Framework

Discussion - Local Relevance and Support for Northwestern Germany: The SAWA example provides insights that can benefit OOWV's efforts in sustainable water management:

- **Adaptive Measures:** Learning from adaptive strategies and decision-making processes can support OOWV in identifying entry points for integrated water management.
- **Circular Economy Potential:** Embracing sustainable water management practices with circular economy potential aligns with OOWV's goals.
- **Stakeholder Engagement:** Understanding the collaboration and engagement strategies employed by SAWA can help OOWV effectively involve relevant parties.

Support for DECISO Pilot Project: SAWA's experience offers support to OOWV's efforts in the following ways:

- **Adaptive Strategies:** Learning from SAWA's adaptive strategies provides starting points for consideration for sustainable water management in the OOWV association area.
- **Decision Support Database:** Insights from SAWA's decision support database can inform OOWV's decision-making processes.
- **Sustainable Water Management:** Lessons learned from SAWA's sustainable water management practices can inspire similar initiatives in OOWV.
- **Replicability and Transferability:** The practical experience, especially with regard to sustainable retention basin concepts and innovative drainage systems, provides a range of interesting starting points. OOWV can benefit from the extensive data and variables used to assess water bodies, retention basins, and rainwater harvesting potential.

Conclusion:

SAWA's example of sustainable water management and circular economy integration provides valuable insights and strategies. By leveraging adaptive measures, decision support databases, and education, OOWV can enhance its approach to sustainable water management. The experience gained from SAWA's practices can foster innovation and resilience in OOWV's pilot project.

GP11. Rooftop Garden and Greenhouse Urban Farming

Discussion - Local Relevance and Support for Northwestern Germany: The practice of Nature-Based Rainwater Management aligns with OOWV's goals for sustainable water management and urban resilience. By exploring similar strategies, the pilot project in Northwestern Germany can achieve the following:

- **Reduced Surface Runoff:** Implementing rain gardens and on-site infiltration can mitigate surface runoff, contributing to flood prevention.
- **Enhanced Urban Greenery:** Incorporating rooftop gardens and green infrastructure can improve the quality of urban spaces and promote well-being.
- **Water Conservation:** Utilizing rainwater for urban farming and other purposes reduces dependence on external water sources.
- **Cross-Fertilization:** Learning from the Turin example and the experiences of other projects can inspire innovative solutions for rainwater management in the region.

Support for DECISO Pilot Project: The Turin example provides valuable insights and support for the DECISO pilot project in Northwestern Germany:

- **Technical Expertise:** Learning from the implementation of rooftop gardens, aeroponic systems, and rain gardens can guide the design and execution of similar systems.
- **Stakeholder Engagement:** Understanding the collaboration required among authorities, suppliers, and citizens is crucial for successful implementation.
- **Monitoring and Analysis:** The monitoring approach used in Turin, including water quality analysis and data collection, can inform the development of similar systems in Northwestern Germany.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, the Nature-Based Rainwater Management practice exemplifies how innovative approaches can enhance urban water management and promote sustainability. Adapting this practice to the regional context of Northwestern Germany will contribute to improved rainwater utilization, reduced flooding risks, and the creation of more resilient and liveable urban environments.

GP12. Evolving Regions Collaborative Roadmapping

Discussion - Local Relevance and Support for Northwestern Germany: Evolving Regions provides insights relevant to OOWV's goals:

- **Collaborative Framework:** OOWV can leverage collaboration among diverse stakeholders to foster climate resilience.
- **Stakeholder Engagement:** Learning from stakeholder involvement strategies can enhance OOWV's engagement approach.
- **Climate Data Utilization:** The practice highlights the importance of using regional climate data for informed decision-making, aligning with OOWV's data-driven approach.

Support for DECISO Pilot Project: Evolving Regions offers support to OOWV's efforts:

- **Collaborative Strategies:** Learning from stakeholder cooperation methods enhances OOWV's collaborative approaches.
- **Roadmap Development:** Insights from roadmap creation can guide OOWV in strategic planning for climate adaptation measures.

- **Data Utilization:** Leveraging regional climate data aligns with OOWV's aim to base decisions on accurate information.

Conclusion:

Evolving Regions' collaborative climate resilience roadmapping offers OOWV valuable strategies and insights to foster climate-resilient regions. By integrating stakeholder engagement, climate data, and regional collaboration, OOWV can enhance its approach to climate adaptation, ensuring a sustainable and resilient future for the Northwestern Germany region. The experience shared through this practice can inform OOWV's efforts and promote positive climate outcomes.

8.4. Pilot 4. WESTERN MACEDONIA

GP 13. Use of alternative raw materials and fuels in cement industry (TITAN Group Industry)

Discussion - Local Relevance and Support for Amynteo territory in Western Macedonia: For DHCA aiming to implement a circular economy project that exploits biomass and residues/wastes, this good practice example offers many useful insights. The use of alternative raw materials and fuels in cement Industry aligns with DHCA's main objective to produce district heating from other sources than lignite. By adopting similar activities, DHCA can:

- **Reduce dependence on conventional resources.**
- **Reduce CO₂ emissions**, since RDF/SRF use are lower than those of fossil fuels because RDF/SRF contains a significant percentage of biomass.
- **Contribute to Commission's guidelines** for diverting more than 90% of waste from landfills by 2035

Support for DECISO Pilot Project: RDF/SRF use showcased in practise that can be explored to the DECISO pilot project in Western Macedonia:

- **Expertise Sharing & Feasibility Assessment:** More deep dives in the topic with Titan could be very useful to explore technical hardships and obstacles for the RDF/SRF use.
- **Stakeholder Engagement:** The issue of the use of RDF/SRF has recently started to concern public opinion and a step-by-step consultation process should be carefully drawn to engage local and regional stakeholders.
- **Technical Guidance:** New installations or upgrades to the existing infrastructure with the use of alternative fuels can allow DHCP plant to reach record thermal substitution levels and contribute to local waste-management efforts.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, this GP example is the best-case study already tested in Greece regarding the use of RDF/SRF. DHCA is following very closely all updates of the GP, as also the related legal issues. For DHCA is an opportunity to explore the increased use of lower-carbon fuels that could replace non-renewable fossil fuels.

GP 14. Poznan Energy from Waste Plant, Poland

Discussion - Local Relevance and Support for Amynteo territory in Western Macedonia: For DHCA aiming to implement a circular economy project that exploits biomass and residues/wastes, this good practice example offers various useful insights and is very similar to GP13, but implemented for a longer period in another EU country. It is a real interesting circular economy concept combined with energy sector development and environmental protection, matching DHCA framework and strategic plan. By adopting similar activities, DHCA can in addition than those described for the GP13 conclusions:

- **Participate in waste management plans** as an integral part of the regional & national energy and climate plans.

- **Can contribute to energy utilisation of residues** above landfilling in hierarchy of mixed municipal waste management.

Support for DECISO Pilot Project: Similar energy efficiency obligation schemes and alternative policy measures can be explored to the DECISO pilot project in Western Macedonia:

- **Expertise Sharing & Feasibility Assessment:** The GP consists of a waste-to-energy plant complying with the relevant national and European standards, including the EU Directive on waste incineration. The joint venture that was chosen by the city of Poznań to carry out the design, construction, financing, and operation of the plant over a period of 25 years is to be explored by DHCA.
- **Stakeholder Engagement:** Waste disposal alternatives open discussions need to be based on similar tested EU practises.
- **Technical Guidance:** The plant is designed to convert about 216,000 tonnes of waste per year into electricity and district heat. More deep dives on detailed technical issues could be explored by DHCA.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, this GP example is another best-case study already tested in an EU country regarding energy-from-waste tested solutions.

GP 15. Econotre eco-notre

Discussion - Local Relevance and Support for Amynteo territory in Western Macedonia: For DHCA aiming to implement a circular economy project that exploits biomass and residues/wastes, this good practice example offers various useful insights. Econotre consists of an interesting GP since it is local circular economy hub that gathers all treatment modes in a single site: (Mechanical treatment, composting, thermal treatment, energy recovery unit). DHCA can mainly explore in addition those presented for GP 13 and 14:

- The efforts set by Bessières town hall and Econotre to generate alternative renewable energy to support the energy transition and local socio-economic development. Similar collaborations are also needed between DHCA and the municipality of Amynteo.
- The sorting center features that produces secondary raw material for energy recovery with treatment of non-recyclables to produce electricity and heat.

Support for DECISO Pilot Project: The facility uses incineration to recover the value from household waste and it can be explored to the DECISO pilot project in Western Macedonia:

- **Expertise Sharing & Feasibility Assessment:** The GP processing method exploits the energy generated by burning the waste to produce electricity and heat that is among the interests of DHCA. The GP has strong evidence of success that are of added value for other organisations exploring similar tested solutions in Europe.
- **Stakeholder Engagement:** Waste disposal alternatives open discussions need to be based on similar tested EU practises.
- **Technical Guidance:** Econotre represents 30,000 tonnes of recyclable household waste sorted, 45,000 tonnes of bottom ash recovered, 8,000 tonnes of green waste recovered, and 3,500 tonnes of compost produced every year. More deep dives on detailed technical issues could be explored by DHCA.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, this GP example is another best-case study already tested in an EU country regarding energy-from-waste tested solutions.

GP 16. Innovative Technologies for Ecological and Efficient Pyrolysis of Waste treatment

Discussion - Local Relevance and Support for Amynteo territory in Western Macedonia: For DHCA aiming to implement a circular economy project that exploits biomass and residues/wastes, this good practice

example offers additional useful insights, based on a recycling station that uses pyrolysis technology to transform industrial biomass, household waste and sewage sludge into bio-gas, bio-oil and biochar in addition to creating thermal energy for hot water and air generators. DHCA can mainly explore in addition those presented for GP 13, 14 & 15:

- The efforts set by ecoHORNET that has created the W2E innovative recycling eco station using pyrolysis as the main chemical process.
- Support for DECISO Pilot Project: The facility produces agri-pellets made from waste and residues from agriculture, including vegetal and animal substances, forestry and related industries, as well as the biodegradable part of industrial and municipal waste are combusted to generate energy and it can be explored to the DECISO pilot project in Western Macedonia:
- **Expertise Sharing & Feasibility Assessment:** The GP showcased that the ecoHORNET company has developed and patented very innovative technologies and equipment's for Waste 2 Energy Treatment Stations. Another interesting issue is that the operating costs are minimal, the installation is self-sustainable from an energetic point of view and the activity is profitable.
- **Stakeholder Engagement:** Waste disposal alternatives open discussions need to be based on similar tested EU practises.
- **Technical Guidance:** Since DHCA already operates a plant for the combustion of a mixture of agricultural residues and lignite, more deep dives on detailed technical issues could be explored for this GP.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, this GP example is another best-case study already tested in an EU country regarding energy-from-waste tested solutions, based on pyrolysis.

GP 17. The Revised National Waste Management Plan for the period 2020-2030

Discussion - Local Relevance and Support for Amynteo territory in Western Macedonia: For DHCA aiming to implement a circular economy project that exploits biomass and residues/wastes, this specific and additional good practice example offers critical inputs on all recent Waste Management legislation that provide support for energy recovery from waste, including the retrofitting of Waste Treatment Units (WTPs) into Waste Recovery Units (WREUs). DHCA can mainly explore:

- The energetic valorization of secondary fuels and residues is also promoted through the official responsible authorities in national level.

Support for DECISO Pilot Project: The GP is a legislation process ongoing to address the framework for energy recovery from waste in Greece and it should be explored to the DECISO pilot project in Western Macedonia mainly for the:

- **Stakeholder Engagement:** Waste disposal alternatives open discussions in Western Macedonia.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, this GP can facilitate the Western Macedonia regional pilot to retrofit its installations towards the use of wastes and residues as fuels for thermal energy production.

The results of this Deliverable are summarised in [Annex III](#).

9. Bibliography

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<https://www.vanharen.net/blog/best-practice-model-framework-method-guidance-standard-towards-consistent-use-terminology/>

<https://www.interregeurope.eu/policy-solutions/good-practices>

<https://projects2014-2020.interregeurope.eu/2lives/good-practices/>

[Good practices | European Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform \(europa.eu\)](#)

10. Annex I. GOOD PRACTICES TEMPLATE

The Task Leader PDM, as responsible for the current Deliverable, provided the partners with the following template for the collection of Good Practices.

Good Practice Description for the **DECISO** project

Concentrate on various types of **barriers** (costs, supply chain, lack of cooperation, technical gaps, quality compromise, etc.) that could hinder the development of CE value chains.

Criteria to follow
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: The practice should address Circular Economy as the main sector
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Effectiveness: The practice must produce mostly measurable results during a specific time period
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transfer Potential - Replicability: The practice could be replicable elsewhere or have at least partly a strong transfer potential
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholders & Community Involvement: The practice must involve satisfactory collaboration between several & core stakeholders & community members.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Observability: The practice results are easy to find / explore or demonstrated
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Political commitment: The practice must have support from the relevant national, regional, or local related authorities / organisations

1. Author contact information	
Full Name	
Email	
Telephone	
2. Organisation providing the Description	
Country	
Region	

Website		
3. Public or private body responsible of the Practice		
Name of the organisation being the main public or private body in charge of this practice		
Location of the responsible public or private body:	<i>Country</i>	
	<i>Region/City</i>	

4. Good Practice general information		
Title of the Practice		
Web link		
Timescale (start/end month/year)		
Name the project where this practice come is coming from		
Name the project acronym		
Thematic objective of the Practice		
Geographical scope of the Practice	<i>Local/ Regional / National / International</i>	
Location of the Practice	<i>Country</i>	
	<i>Region/City</i>	
5. Good Practice elements		
Abstract of the Practice	<i>[300 characters]</i>	
Details of the Practice – Main steps & activities	<i>[2.500 characters]</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>What is the issue/topic addressed and the context which triggered the introduction of the practice for DECISO partners/promoters?</i> - <i>How does the practice reach its objectives and how it is/was implemented?</i> - <i>Who are the main stakeholders and beneficiaries of the practice?</i> 	

Resources needed for the Practice	[500 characters]
Evidence of success (measurable results achieved)	[700 characters]
What worked well or not?	[700 characters]
Transfer Potential – Replicability	[1.500 characters]

11. Annex II. TEMPLATE FOR INTERVIEWS AND STORYTELLING INITIATIVES WITH EUROPEAN, NATIONAL AND LOCAL STAKEHOLDERS AND WITH PEOPLE FROM SISTER PROJECTS

The following template was provided also by PDM in order to help partners to collect information regarding good practices and case studies opportunities during interviews.

Methodology suggestions	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Methodology: “Light” Interviews (mostly like round table discussions) based on a semi-structured questionnaire provided as an informal template to follow during the interview 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Our focus on each case study opportunities or good practice is on: Social, economic, legislative / regulatory and financial context that have determined their success. We need to identify and discuss: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ good practices and case studies opportunities at the European level, ➤ how they can contribute at local level, and ➤ what kind of support can provide to the project 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Where and when: (1) M6 (April 2023): During the participatory workshop that will be organized at the European level by ACR+ in Brussels, involving European experts of circular economy and sister projects. (2) M8 (June 2023): During the national participatory workshop that will be organized in each piloting area 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Who and how many: Two case studies of opportunities or good practices per pilot partner/region. 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Output: 1 filled form per each good practice or case study opportunities 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Suggested semi-structured questionnaire: (1) Fill in parts 3,4 before the interview process: During the interview, please: (2) Clarify any possible Social and economic context. (3) Clarify any possible Legislative / regulatory context. and 	

(4) Clarify any Financial context.
that have determined the good practice or case study opportunity success.

Note:

Please, have in mind that depending on the case or practice profile, you can skip a context that is probably not appropriate.

1. Author contact information

Full Name	
Email	
Telephone	

2. Organisation providing the Description

Country	
Region	
Website	

3. Public or private body responsible of the Practice or Case Study

Name of the organisation being the main public or private body in charge		
Location of the responsible public or private body:	Country	
	Region/City	

4. Good Practice or Case Study general information

Title		
Web link		
Timescale (start/end month/year)		
Name the project where it is coming from		
Name the 4. Good Practice or Case Study acronym		
Thematic objective / main sector		
Geographical scope	<i>Local/ Regional / National / International</i>	
Location	Country	
	Region/City	

5. Good Practice or Case Study abstract and contexts that have determined the good practice or case study opportunities success

Abstract of the Practice (Short description of the Practice)	<i>[300 characters]</i>
Social and economic context	<i>[1.500 characters]</i>
Legislative / regulatory context	<i>[1.500 characters]</i>

Financial context	<i>[1.500 characters]</i>
How can it contribute at local level?	<i>[700 characters]</i>
What kind of support can provide to the project?	<i>[700 characters]</i> <i>a) Shared Communication</i> <i>b) Use of tools / solution</i> <i>c) Shared exploitation</i> <i>d) ...etc..</i>

1. Annex III. SUMMARY OF DELIVERABLE 1.2

Pilot #	Topic	Title of the Good Practice	Geographical Scope	Transfer Potential - Replicability as Opportunity for each partner	Clear evidence of success	Opportunities at European and National Level	Comments
Pilot 1	Strategic Framework for Financial Schemes	PROFI Environment (PROFI Umwelt) (single beneficiary) PROFi Environment Transfer (PROFI Umwelt Transfer) (cooperation projects)	Regional	Yes	Yes	Strong transfer potential, replication considered as opportunity for organization and others at national and European level	
Pilot 1	Strategic Framework for Financial Schemes	Circular Cities (past programme) ClimAccelerator (EIT Climate-KIC)	International	Not clear	Yes	Opportunity as long as a combination of an accelerator programme and funding are possible	
Pilot 1	Strategic Framework for Financial Schemes	BNW circular hubs	National	Yes	Yes	Strong transfer potential, replication considered as opportunity for organization and others at national and European level	High replicability with need for funding and regional contact points.
Pilot 1	Strategic Framework for Financial Schemes	IFB Innovations starter (IFB Innovationsstarter)	Regional	Yes	Yes	Strong transfer potential, replication considered as opportunity for organization and others at national and European level	Funding schemes are replicable; criteria may need to be adapted to national requirements.

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Pilot #	Topic	Title of the Good Practice	Geographical Scope	Transfer Potential - Replicability as Opportunity for each partner	Clear evidence of success	Opportunities at European and National Level	Comments
Pilot 1	Strategic Framework for Financial Schemes	circularinvest	International	Yes	Yes	Strong transfer potential, replication considered as opportunity for organization and others at national and European level	Funding and consortium needed.
Pilot 2	Circular Agri-food Bussiness Models	URSA Project - Alqueva By-Products Recirculation Units	Regional	Yes	Yes	Strong transfer potential in every country and region where sustainable agriculture is a priority and where there are large irrigated agricultural areas	
Pilot 2	Circular Agri-food Bussiness Models	AgroPaper a sustainable and biodegradable solution for the agricultural mulching technique	International	Yes	Not clear	Entities have the opportunity to promote this alternative in the agri-food sector and protect the environment, fulfilling European Green Deal	
Pilot 2	Circular Agri-food Bussiness Models	Fossil-Energy-Free Technologies and Strategies (FEFTS)	International	Yes	Yes	Opportunities for reduction of fossil energy use in energy consumption of agricultural buildings, tools, and fuel consumption of vehicles	

Pilot #	Topic	Title of the Good Practice	Geographical Scope	Transfer Potential - Replicability as Opportunity for each partner	Clear evidence of success	Opportunities at European and National Level	Comments
Pilot 3	Optimise Rainwater use	Rainwater Treatment Systems	National	Not clear	Yes	N/A	Opportunity for the Northwestern Gerany to explore similar smart solutions, considering its regional capabilities and rainwater utilization potential. Specific approach needed for each company's site.
Pilot 3	Optimise Rainwater use	SAWA's Climate Resilience Framework	International	Yes	Yes	N/A	Strong transfer options with potential benefits for sustainable flood retention basin concept. Opportunity to to facilitate climate adaptation through stakeholder involvement, data-driven decisions, and strategic planning.
Pilot 3	Optimise Rainwater use	Rooftop Garden and Greenhouse Urban Farming	International	Not clear	No	N/A	Practical example of intermediate storage and use of precipitation; improvement of urban space quality and safety. Opportunity to leverage local resources more effectively.
Pilot 3	Optimise Rainwater use	Evolving Regions Collaborative Roadmapping	International	Yes	Yes	N/A	Framework uniting stakeholders for climate adaptation actions.
Pilot 4	Decarbonization and post-lignite transition	Use of alternative raw materials and fuels in cement Industry (TITAN GROUP Industry)	National	Yes	Yes	Opportunity to explore the increased use of lower-carbon fuels that could replace non-renewable fossil fuels.	High transfer potential in national contexts with alternative raw materials and fuels.

Pilot #	Topic	Title of the Good Practice	Geographical Scope	Transfer Potential - Replicability as Opportunity for each partner	Clear evidence of success	Opportunities at European and National Level	Comments
Pilot 4	Decarbonization and post-lignite transition	Poznan Energy from Waste Plant Poland	International	Yes	Yes	Opportunity to learn from the operation of plant /successful technical example in the production of thermal energy from municipal solid waste	Replicable approach for energy-from-waste plants.
Pilot 4	Decarbonization and post-lignite transition	Econotre eco-centre	International	Yes	Yes	Opportunity to learn from the operation of the local circular economy hub that gathers all treatment modes in a single site: Mechanical treatment, composting, thermal treatment, energy recovery unit	High transfer potential for eco-centres.
Pilot 4	Decarbonization and post-lignite transition	Innovative Technologies for Ecological and Efficient Pyrolysis of Waste Treatment	International	Yes	Not clear	Opportunity i) for the energy production using exclusively biomass and ii) for combustion by products to become secondary raw materials	Innovative pyrolysis technologies with replication opportunities.
Pilot 4	Decarbonization and post-lignite transition	The Revised National Waste Management Plan for the period 2020-2030	National	Yes	Not yet	Opportunity at national level to decrease the % of wastes that are buried in the regional landfill and at the same time increasing the energy production	National Waste Management Plan with potential for improvement.

